

Review

The soil-management interface: An interdisciplinary review bridging natural capital, ecosystem services, and sustainable development

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ABSTRACT

The nature–business nexus is increasingly recognized for its vital role in sustaining ecosystem services and advancing sustainable development. This paper provides an interdisciplinary review of research at the intersection of soil science and the Business, Management, and Accounting (BMA) domain. Using bibliometric tools, thematic and temporal analysis, and a knowledge graph, the study traces the evolution of four key themes (linked to fifteen sub-themes): Soil Pollution Management and Environmental Remediation, Life Cycle and Environmental Impact, Sustainability and Ecosystems, and Agricultural Practices and Efficiency. These are grouped into two overarching domains: (1) Soil Health, Environmental, and Technical Management and (2) Circular Economy, Ecosystem Services, and Sustainable Development. The review highlights the emerging role of soil as natural capital within broader systems thinking frameworks that integrate environmental stewardship and socio-economic goals. It demonstrates that soil health management is central to the provision and regulation of ecosystem services, with implications for climate action, food security, and sustainability transitions. The findings suggest that BMA and natural science scholars should adopt holistic and forward-looking approaches that align short-term agricultural needs with long-term sustainability objectives. Such integration is critical for enhancing soil ecosystem resilience, informing public policy, and embedding soil stewardship within sustainable development strategies.

1. Introduction

“The nation that destroys its soil, destroys itself.”

- Franklin D. Roosevelt

Soil, as a key element of natural capital, is one of the most vital components of the planet’s ecosystem, playing a crucial role throughout human civilization (Brevik et al., 2018). As part of natural capital—defined as the stock of natural assets such as soils, air, water bodies, and forests that generate valuable ecosystem goods and services over time (Dominati et al., 2014)—soil underpins a wide range of functions essential for human and ecological well-being. From ancient times, it has served as the foundation for agriculture, settlements, and the growth of societies. It has provided essential ecosystem services, including supporting, regulating, provisioning, and cultural services (Kosanic and Petzold, 2020; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2003; Shrestha et al., 2023), enabling human societies to thrive and sustain themselves over millennia. However, this close relationship has not always been

beneficial for the soil. The Industrial Revolution brought significant changes, with increased demand for resources leading to intensive farming and widespread land use changes, resulting in practices that exploited soil without replenishing it. This unsustainable exploitation led to soil degradation, pollution, and a decline in soil health (Wu et al., 2018).

As awareness of these issues grew, research focused on understanding decontamination, soil pollution and remediation strategies. Scholars have started investigating negative factors affecting soil and finding ways to mitigate these adverse effects. Scientists aimed to identify sources of contamination, types of pollutants, and methods to cleanse and restore soil quality (Laha et al., 2009). These foundational attempts helped build a more nuanced understanding of soil and its critical role in sustaining ecosystems and environmental safety (Biabani et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2020; Tang et al., 2019; Torres et al., 2021).

While soil studies were evolving, two streams of research appeared. On the one hand, soil scientists concentrated on soil-structure interaction, mechanical properties, stabilization, and remediation (Biabani

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et al., 2023). On the other hand, interdisciplinary scholars began exploring the economic implications and developing models to quantify the costs associated with soil pollution and the benefits of soil conservation (Cai et al., 2021; Evans et al., 2022), and examining the economic viability of remediation efforts and the long-term impacts of soil health on agricultural productivity and food security (Hinge et al., 2021).

In recent years, the demand for sustainability has become increasingly prominent, shifting the focus toward soil and environmental health. The United Nations has dedicated a specific Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) to this cause: Life on Land (SDG 15) (UNGA, 2015). This goal emphasizes the protection, restoration, and sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, forest management, combating desertification, and halting biodiversity loss, all to ensure the health of the planet's land resources (UNGA, 2015). Achieving this requires robust managerial systems and approaches at various levels. However, research addressing sustainability from both soil management and business perspectives has often been fragmented and lacking in cohesion (Ingram et al., 2022).

Technological innovations to enhance soil use and productivity have introduced additional complexity to the issue. The potential for unintended consequences means these technologies must be carefully managed to ensure they contribute to sustainable soil management (Schirpke et al., 2023). Issues such as adverse effects, increased resource dependency, soil degradation, ecosystem disruption, and economic inequality must be considered (Toor et al., 2021). In the same vein, innovations like agricultural robots and precision agriculture have revolutionized farming practices (Aubert et al., 2012a,b; Li et al., 2022), enabling more efficient use of soil resources and increasing crop yields. However, while these innovations may boost short-term yields, they could compromise long-term soil health and traditional farming knowledge. This highlights the need for balanced, sustainable business approaches that integrate both modern and traditional practices (Martinho, 2019).

Despite extensive research, a significant gap remains in understanding soil studies within the Business, Management, and Accounting (BMA) subject area. Addressing this gap is crucial, as integrating soil and ecosystem considerations into the BMA field can help achieve sustainable development goals by aligning ecosystem services, environmental management, landscape management, human well-being, business responsibility, productivity, organizational structures and processes, and economic valuation for informed conservation and development decisions (Braat and de Groot, 2012; Brander et al., 2024; Costanza and Daly, 1992; Keesstra et al., 2018; Martinho, 2019; Shrestha et al., 2023). Soil research through a business lens aids in strategic planning, risk management, environmental-economic accounting, and decision-making with impacts on synergies among ecosystem services and the optimal mix of benefits for both nature and people (Comte et al., 2022; de Groot et al., 2022; Ingram et al., 2022; Normyle et al., 2023; Shrestha et al., 2023). It has potential implications for various sectors such as agriculture, food, and construction while addressing value chain stability and long-term profitability (Villa-Cox et al., 2023). Moreover, this interdisciplinary approach helps manage costs, optimize resource use, and align with sustainability objectives, thereby promoting long-term economic viability and environmental stewardship (Braat and de Groot, 2012; Ingram et al., 2022; Keesstra et al., 2018; Martinho, 2019).

To address this gap, this study aims to offer a comprehensive view of soil research within the BMA field, uncovering themes, trends, and research directions through thematic and temporal analyses. This integrative approach leverages bibliometric tools to provide valuable insights into the structure and dynamics of scientific research, supporting a wide range of stakeholders in making informed decisions and advancing knowledge (Donthu et al., 2021; Zupic and Čater, 2015). Specifically, the study addresses the following research questions: 1) **How has soil research evolved within BMA?** 2) **What are the main themes and trends at the soil-BMA intersection?** 3) **How can these insights guide interdisciplinary research in the future?**

Through these questions, the study develops a comprehensive map of soil studies in the BMA context, highlighting the knowledge structure of research and identifying gaps, trends, and potential directions for investigation (Salimi et al., 2021). This mapping offers compelling insights into the interdisciplinary connections between soil and management, guiding future research and policy-makers to ensure the sustainability of soil resources and ecosystems, thereby strengthening the socio-economy and eco-environment (Rasmussen et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2018).

The next section details the methodology, followed by the research findings and the development of the discussion. We utilize a knowledge graph to synthesize and interpret the key themes and patterns identified across the literature. This analysis is complemented by actionable insights and recommendations for future research and policymakers.

2. Methodology

This section details our methodology for retrieving scientific documents that shape research within the intersection of soil and BMA studies. Subsequently, we elucidate the use of bibliometric analysis and articulate the rationale for its application in examining this research.

2.1. Data set configuration

The initial literature search was conducted in November 2023 using the Scopus database, encompassing all available years within its repository. Scopus was chosen due to its recognized broader coverage across various research disciplines compared to other databases such as the “Web of Science” (Mongeon and Paul-Hus, 2016). Empirical evidence suggests that employing multiple databases does not necessarily enhance result quality (Harzing & Alakangas, 2016). Fig. 1 illustrates the steps involved in configuring the dataset.

The keyword “soil” was utilised as the search term, confined to the TITLE-ABS-KEY field to ensure the inclusion of studies where soil featured prominently in their title, abstract, and/or keywords. This search query yielded 1,317,788 documents. To refine the scope, we limited the results to the subject areas falling under BMA studies while excluding non-English documents. The final dataset comprised 6910 documents.

2.2. Bibliometric methods

This study applies bibliometric methods to review and analyse the research done at the intersection of soil and BMA studies. Bibliometric analysis concentrates on summarizing the bibliometric and intellectual structure of a field by analysing social and structural relationships among research constituents, such as words and topics (Donthu et al., 2021). By leveraging bibliographic data to objectively evaluate scientific literature, these methods unveil “invisible colleges”—informal research networks (De Solla Price, 1965). Reflecting authors' judgments over time, citation images illuminate the structure and dynamics of scientific fields (Zupic and Čater, 2015). In contrast to narrative literature reviews, which can be influenced by researcher bias and lack rigour, bibliometric methods offer a systematic and quantitative approach to describing, evaluating, and monitoring published research (Tranfield et al., 2003; Zupic and Čater, 2015).

Bibliometric methods serve two key purposes: performance analysis and science mapping, revealing the structure and development of fields. While leveraging science maps as a starting point, the paper emphasizes that interpretation strategies should align with the specific focus of the research (Zupic and Čater, 2015). In this case, the emphasis is on understanding literature's thematic and temporal dynamics, emphasizing how various keywords and concepts relate and influence each other over time in BMA research within the soil context.

Fig. 1. Dataset configuration.

3. Bibliometric analyses and results

Following a performance overview, this section presents a comprehensive keyword (co-word/co-occurrence) analysis. We create network visualizations of the most frequent terms from both the All-keyword and Authors-keyword perspectives, identifying key overarching and thematic clusters. Subsequently, a review of influential papers within each thematic cluster is conducted. Further insights are provided by examining underlying key conceptual trends over time.

3.1. Performance overview

By using Scopus-based metrics, we assess the scholarly output within the domain of soil research, specifically focusing on the subject area of BMA. This overview encompasses an examination of various parameters, including the number of documents published annually, the top productive sources, and the affiliations of contributing institutions. This quantitative evaluation offers insights into the trajectory and impact of research endeavours within the field (Alerasoul et al., 2022b; Zupic and

Čater, 2015).

Our investigation reveals a notable trend of expansion in soil research output, particularly evident in the substantial surge observed since 2016, peaking in 2019, followed by a slight downturn in subsequent years. This trend underscores the growing significance and scholarly interest in soil science within the purview of BMA studies. Notably, the volume of publications surged dramatically from 227 papers in 2016 to 734 papers in 2019, signifying a threefold increase within this period (Fig. 2).

Examining the landscape of scholarly contributions within this subject area, our analysis identifies the “Journal of Cleaner Production” as the primary disseminator of BMA-related soil research, with 1841 publications attributed to the research area studied. Known for its transdisciplinary focus on sustainable development, environmental technical processes, and sustainability research, the journal plays a crucial role in advancing sustainable soil management. This is followed by “Applied Geography” with 215 publications.

Furthermore, our scrutiny extends to institutional affiliations driving research productivity in this field. Notably, Chinese institutions emerge

Fig. 2. The number of published documents per year (source: Scopus).

as leading contributors, with the Chinese Academy of Sciences occupying the top position. This observation underscores China's significant investment and commitment to mitigating land degradation, advancing agricultural, and soil management, and restoring ecosystem services (Kong et al., 2023). Additionally, European representation is notable, with Wageningen University and Research ranking prominently among the top five institutions, featuring its dedication to natural and environmental sciences (Fig. 3).

3.2. Keyword (Co-word/Co-occurrence) analysis

Keyword, co-word, or co-occurrence analysis helps to explore the existing or future relationships among topics in a research field by focusing on the written content of the publication itself. The analysis assumes that words that frequently appear together have a thematic relationship with one another. Hence, analysis of the co-occurrence of keywords helps understand a field's research direction and central themes (Donthu et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2021).

This study utilizes VOSviewer software (Van Eck and Waltman, 2010) to examine the co-occurrence network of keywords. Employing the Visualization Of Similarities (VOS) clustering technique, VOSviewer maps spatial relationships among items in the network. The software accomplishes this task by minimizing a function based on a similarity measure (AS_{ij}) between items, expressed by the formula (Strozzi et al., 2017):

$$AS_{ij} = \frac{c_{ij}}{c_i c_j}$$

In this context, c_{ij} denotes the co-occurrence measure of keywords i and j in the same document, while c_i and c_j signify the expected number of co-occurrences of i and j , assuming their co-occurrences are statistically independent. This similarity measure, incorporated by VOSviewer, effectively captures relationships and clustering patterns within the co-occurrence keyword network.

In this study, we employ a comprehensive approach to keyword analysis by utilizing both the All-keywords and Author's-keywords settings (Coulter et al., 1998; Courtial, 1994; Ravikumar et al., 2015). This dual-setting strategy allows us to capture a nuanced view of the literature (Khasseh et al., 2017) on soil within the BMA context. All-keywords approach provides a broad perspective, encompassing terms associated with each publication, while Author's keywords offer insights into the specific terms chosen by the authors to represent the core themes of their work. By combining these settings, we aim to gain a holistic understanding of the prevalent topics, trends, and relationships within literature.

The impact of adjusting filter values in co-occurrence analysis is substantial, influencing the equilibrium between focus and comprehensiveness. Higher filter values result in a more focused map with fewer but prominent keywords, while lower values generate a more extensive map with potentially less distinct patterns. In our keyword analysis, we employ a nuanced approach by applying distinct frequency thresholds for the All-keywords and the Author's keywords settings. For All-keywords, a higher threshold of 80 occurrences was chosen to capture robust and frequently occurring terms across the entire dataset, ensuring a focus on keywords that hold substantial significance within the broader context of business-related soil literature; it was selected after testing different cut-off points, providing a broader context and a clearer representation of the key themes. For the Author's keywords, the default threshold of 5 occurrences in VOSviewer was used, allowing closer attention to keywords explicitly chosen by authors. By tailoring the frequency thresholds to the characteristics of each keyword set, we aimed to uncover both broad trends within the overall literature and nuanced emphases within individual author contributions, providing a comprehensive perspective on the BMA aspects of soil research.

Subsequently, we reviewed each of the clusters identified by meticulously examining the top 100 highly cited relevant papers on Scopus,

filtering them based on the most frequently occurring terms within each cluster. This process facilitates a focused analysis of the central themes and emerging trends within literature.

To enrich our understanding of the literature landscape, we conducted a temporal analysis by employing overlay visualization in VOSviewer for both the All-keywords and the Author's keywords settings. This allows us to visually explore the evolution of concepts and themes over time by analyzing the Average Publication Year (APY) of terms (Van Eck and Waltman, 2023), individually and collectively, used by authors and those automatically extracted from publications. By overlaying these visualizations, we aim to provide a temporal perspective on the central terms and themes and enhance the interpretability and comprehensiveness of our analysis within BMA-related soil research.

3.2.1. Network visualization of most frequent terms – all-keyword analysis

The visualization of all-keyword analysis resulting from the optimized filter setting is presented in Fig. 4. Each node in the visualization represents a keyword, and its size is proportionate to occurrences, aiding in the identification of central themes within BMA-related soil literature. Larger nodes indicate more frequent occurrences, highlighting the prominence of specific keywords. Edge thickness between nodes indicates the strength of co-occurrence, with thicker lines revealing robust associations and frequent appearances together in the literature. This provides insights into the intensity of relationships among different thematic elements. The spatial arrangement of nodes reflects algorithmically determined proximity based on co-occurrence patterns, where closer nodes demonstrate stronger associations, while farther nodes may suggest weaker ties. The diverse colors in the visualization represent distinct clusters of keywords with robust co-occurrence patterns, delineating thematic groups where keywords share notable associations. The size of each cluster indicates its relative significance and the interconnectedness of associated keywords (Van Eck and Waltman, 2023).

Complementing this visual representation, Table 1 provides insights into the central soil topics within the BMA. It features the top 30 keywords based on their total link strength and occurrences, offering a snapshot of thematic prominence. The "Total Link Strength" column in Table 1 serves as a key metric, reflecting the cumulative strength of associations between keywords (Van Eck and Waltman, 2023).¹ Noteworthy keywords such as "Soils" (4732), "Life Cycle" (2282), "Agriculture" (2007), "Sustainable Development" (1994), and "Greenhouse Gases" (1985) emerge as not only frequently occurring but also intricately interconnected, highlighting the cohesive thematic structure within the literature.

As the most frequently occurring keyword, "Soils" (1438 occurrences) serves as a foundational term, underlining the primary focus of our review on soil studies. This keyword encapsulates a broad spectrum of research dedicated to soil properties, management, and associated challenges. The prominence of "Life Cycle" (335 occurrences) signifies a significant emphasis on considering the life cycle perspective in the analysis of soil-related processes. This theme highlights a comprehensive approach to studying soil dynamics over time, encompassing various stages from formation to degradation. With "Agriculture" (489 occurrences) being a fundamental theme, our analysis reveals a strong connection between soil studies and agricultural practices. This keyword emphasizes the intricate relationship between soil science and sustainable agricultural management. "Sustainable Development" (445 occurrences) indicates a substantial interest in exploring soil-related issues with respect to sustainability and development. This concept underscores the importance of integrating Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) with soil management practices. The prominence of "Greenhouse Gases" (293 occurrences) also suggests a focus on the

¹ "For a given item, the Links and Total link strength attributes indicate, respectively, the number of links of an item with other items and the total strength of the links of an item with other items." (p. 6).

Fig. 3. The top five productive institutions and organizations (source: Scopus).

Fig. 4. Network visualization of most frequent terms (Constructed via VOSViewer v.1.6.20 for the sample N = 6,910, f (frequency) > 80 → 79 keywords).

environmental impact of soil-related activities, particularly linked to climate change (303 occurrences). This keyword highlights the intersection of soil research with broader environmental concerns, as also showcased by several other terms including environmental impact (285 occurrences), ecosystems (216 occurrences), carbon dioxide (203 occurrences), global warming (175 occurrences), and organic carbon (171 occurrences).

Within the network of co-occurring keywords, the term "Sustainable Development" assumes a central position, intricately linked to various thematic elements across clusters. As depicted in Fig. 5, this term serves as a critical nexus, closely connected to key terms such as "agriculture," "agricultural robots," and "water pollution." The network visualization vividly portrays the depth and breadth of these associations, emphasizing the pivotal role of "Sustainable Development" in bridging multiple clusters. Examining link strength values reveals robust interrelationships, with notable linkages to terms like "soils," "life cycle," and "environmental impact." The central placement of "Sustainable Development"

signifies its overarching influence, extending its reach into diverse realms within the management-related soil literature. Whether influencing agricultural practices, technological innovations, or environmental impact assessments, the term acts as a linchpin connecting various facets of research and discourse (Martinho, 2019).

3.2.1.1. *Thematic clusters: unveiling key associations.* Table 2 meticulously delineates four generic clusters identified through co-occurrence analysis, offering a systematic exploration of thematic associations within the realm of BMA-related soil studies. The clusters signify not only the identification of predominant keywords but also the discernment of strong relationships and recurring patterns in the literature. This analysis goes beyond a mere listing of keywords, delving into the nuanced interplay of concepts and the emergence of cohesive themes within the soil studies domain. Our dual perspective, considering both individual keyword prominence and collective clustering, enhances the depth of understanding regarding the critical dimensions and directions

Table 1
Keywords with the highest total link strength and occurrences.

Keyword	Total link strength	Keyword	Occurrences
1. soils	4732	1. soils	1438
2. life cycle	2282	2. agriculture	489
3. agriculture	2007	3. sustainable development	445
4. sustainable development	1994	4. soil pollution	411
5. greenhouse gases	1985	5. crops	356
6. crops	1819	6. life cycle	335
7. soil pollution	1707	7. fertilizers	322
8. fertilizers	1633	8. climate change	303
9. life cycle assessment (lca)	1514	9. greenhouse gases	293
10. environmental impact	1484	10. environmental impact	285
11. cultivation	1331	11. cultivation	275
12. climate change	1312	12. heavy metals	263
13. carbon dioxide	1258	13. Land use	262
14. gas emissions	1255	14. soil conservation	237
15. land use	1233	15. irrigation	218
16. life cycle assessment	1202	16. ecosystems	216
17. global warming	1158	17. groundwater	216
18. ecosystems	1064	18. soil moisture	206
19. soil conservation	1051	19. carbon dioxide	203
20. heavy metals	1012	20. life cycle assessment (lca)	191
21. forestry	1002	21. forestry	187
22. organic carbon	969	22. soil	187
23. irrigation	861	23. gas emissions	177
24. nutrients	819	24. global warming	175
25. economic and social effects	768	25. organic carbon	171
26. environmental management	749	26. nutrients	169
27. economics	739	27. soil testing	168
28. groundwater	738	28. risk assessment	167
29. carbon	737	29. Life cycle assessment	162
30. agricultural robots	730	30. agricultural robots	154

of soil studies in the context of BMA.

Cluster A reflects a strong focus on soil contamination, remediation efforts, and soil quality. Notable terms include heavy metals, contamination, soil pollution, water pollution, remediation, soil mechanics, and stabilization. The cohesive nature of this cluster suggests an emphasis on minimizing soil pollution while improving soil strength and considering innovative environmentally friendly solutions.

Table 2
Thematic clusters of associated keywords (occurrences ≥ 80).

Cluster A: Soil Pollution, Remediation, and Improvement (28 words)	bacteria – bioremediation – compressive strength – contamination – cost effectiveness – costs – drainage – environmental protection – groundwater – health risks – heavy metals – leaching – mathematical models – piles – pollution – pollution control – project management – recycling – remediation – risk assessment – soil – soil mechanics – soil pollution – soil testing – soils – stabilization – wastewater treatment – water pollution
Cluster B: Life Cycle and Environmental Impact (12 words)	carbon – carbon dioxide – carbon footprint – environmental impact – environmental management – eutrophication – gas emissions – global warming – greenhouse gases – life cycle – life cycle assessment – life cycle assessment (lca)
Cluster C: Sustainability and Ecosystems (22 words)	biodiversity – climate change – decision making – ecology – economic and social effects – economics – ecosystems – erosion – forestry – irrigation – land use – remote sensing – soil conservation – soil erosion – soil moisture – sustainability – sustainable development – vegetation – water conservation – water management – water quality – water supply
Cluster D: Agricultural Practices and Efficiency (17 words)	agricultural robots – agriculture – biochar – biomass – composting – crops – cultivation – efficiency – farms – fertilizers – nitrogen – nitrogen fertilizers – nutrients – organic carbon – phosphorus – plants (botany) – productivity

Fig. 5. The fragment of network visualization for the term “sustainable development”.

Cluster B takes a broader view, examining the environmental impact of soil management practices over their entire life cycle, including emissions and sustainability considerations. Life cycle, carbon, carbon dioxide, carbon footprint, and greenhouse gases signify a strong link between soil quality, carbon sequestration, and environmental considerations in the long term.

In the “Sustainability and Ecosystems” cluster (Cluster C), the emphasis shifts towards ecosystem services and diverse facets of sustainability and sustainable development. Keywords such as biodiversity, climate change, economic and social effects, forestry, land use, soil erosion, soil (and water) conservation, sustainability, and sustainable development highlight the interconnectedness of soil studies with broader sustainability concerns. This cluster underlies the imperative of adopting sustainable practices in soil management and embracing ecosystem services.

Finally, Cluster D centers around agricultural practices and efficiency. Terms like agricultural robots, cultivation, fertilizers, biochar, biomass, composting, nutrients, crops, and productivity indicate a focus on technological advancements, use efficiencies, organic farming practices, and higher yields. This cluster reflects the intersection of soil research with agricultural productivity, and how this relationship can be improved through the management of organic processes and use efficiencies.

3.2.1.2. Overlay visualization: unveiling temporal trends. In the realm of bibliometric analysis, overlay visualization serves as a powerful lens, allowing us to scrutinize the temporal evolution of key concepts within the BMA-related soil literature. This technique not only provides a visual spectacle but also illuminates nuanced trends and thematic shifts over time. Employing VOSviewer (Van Eck and Waltman, 2010), we embarked on a journey through the landscape of All-keyword analysis, spanning the years 2000–2024 (Fig. 6).

As we delve into the visualization graph, a distinctive pattern

emerges. Certain terms, such as agricultural robots with Average Publication Year (APY) of 2019, efficiency (APY: 2019), organic carbon (APY: 2019), and nitrogen fertilizers (APY: 2019), adorned in lighter green-yellow hues, signify recent entrants into the scholarly discourse. These words, freshly etched into the narrative, beckon attention as indicators of contemporary research trajectories. Their prominence in the visual landscape suggests a surge in interest, possibly driven by technological advancements, environmental concerns, or evolving agricultural practices.

Contrastingly, older concepts, painted in regal purple, stand as stalwarts of soil literature. Mathematical models (APY: 2003), drainage (APY: 2003), and soil mechanics (APY: 2008) among others, weathered the test of time, retaining their relevance amidst the evolving scholarly landscape. These enduring terms serve as anchors, connecting the past to the present and reminding us of the enduring principles that underpin soil research.

Navigating through the spectrum of greens, from darker shades representing concepts like environmental protection (APY: 2010), and irrigation (APY: 2011) to lighter tones embodying sustainability (APY: 2018) and beyond, we traverse a transitional zone. This zone captures the interplay of enduring principles with the evolving landscape of research interests, forming a bridge between historical foundations and emerging themes.

As we further explore the visual tapestry, terms like contamination (APY: 2014), groundwater (APY: 2014), and plants (APY: 2015) reveal the intricacies of the soil-related narrative. These words, although not the newest, exhibit a vibrancy that suggests sustained interest and evolving dimensions within the discourse. The inclusion of various terms—ranging from cost-effectiveness (APY: 2015) and land use (APY: 2016) to biodiversity (APY: 2017) and decision-making (APY: 2017)—speaks to the dynamic nature of research within the BMA-related soil domain. Each term, positioned within a specific time frame, tells a story of evolving priorities, emerging challenges, and the continuous pursuit

Fig. 6. Overlay visualization of most frequent terms (Constructed via VOSviewer v.1.6.20 for the sample $N = 6,910$, f (frequency) $> 80 \rightarrow 79$ keywords).

of knowledge.

In summary, the overlay visualization not only captures the co-occurrence of keywords but also unveils temporal trends, providing a narrative of the evolving discourse in the management-related soil literature. This analysis not only enhances our understanding of thematic shifts but also guides future exploration, highlighting the need for researchers to engage with both historical foundations and emerging frontiers in this dynamic field.

3.2.2. Network visualization of most frequent terms – authors-keyword analysis

In addition to the comprehensive analysis conducted on all keywords, a detailed examination of author-assigned keywords has revealed fifteen distinctive thematic clusters within the area of BMA-related soil studies (Fig. 7).

The delineation of these clusters offers valuable insights into the multifaceted nature of research endeavours pursued by scholars within the field under study. In the subsequent sub-section, the identified clusters (see Appendix) are systematically categorized and labelled based on their predominant thematic focus and their alignment with one of the four overarching clusters discerned through the comprehensive All-keyword analysis. Furthermore, each cluster is characterized and substantiated by the most pertinent and influential studies representative of the respective cluster. This process entails meticulous curation facilitated by querying Scopus and refining the dataset for each cluster through keyword filtering, guided by an examination of highly occurring terms within the network visualization. Specifically, the top 100 highly cited documents emblematic of each cluster serve as pivotal reference points in elucidating the thematic essence and scholarly significance encapsulated within the clusters.

3.2.2.1. Thematic clusters: unveiling key associations

3.2.2.1.1. Overarching Cluster A: Soil pollution, remediation, and improvement.

- **Cluster A1 (86 words): Soil Stabilization, Construction Materials, and Environmental Protection**

The first cluster provides an extensive exploration of topics related to soil stabilization, construction materials, and recycling. Covering a wide range of keywords, including bearing capacity, compaction, concrete, construction, landfill mining, numerical simulation, recycling, and slope stability, this cluster reflects a multidisciplinary focus on geotechnical aspects, construction practices, material science, recycled waste, and associated methodologies such as the finite-element method (FEM) and scanning electron microscope (SEM). The inclusion of terms like fly ash, embankment, erosion control, geotechnical properties, durability, and green infrastructure suggests an emphasis on environmental risks and signals the role of reinforced soil and recycled waste in the sustainable construction of buildings, roads, highways, etc. (Rahman et al., 2014; Andre et al., 2014; Disfani et al., 2012a,b,c; Karatai et al., 2017; Li et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2019a,b). Additionally, the cluster addresses soil-structure interaction, mechanical properties, stabilization, and remediation (Abbaspour et al., 2019; Dehghan et al., 2019; Hataf et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2021). The diverse range of terms, from bio-cementation to sewage sludge, signifies a research interest both in natural and engineered solutions for soil improvement and construction materials (Rashad, 2017). Overall, this cluster offers insights into the intricate relationship between soil reinforcement, construction materials, recycling and green infrastructure.

Fig. 7. Network visualization of authors' keywords (Constructed via VOSViewer v.1.6.20 for the sample N = 6,910, f (frequency) > 5 → 636 keywords).

• **Cluster A2 (44 words): Soil Pollution and Remediation Techniques**

The “Soil Pollution and Remediation Techniques” cluster offers a comprehensive exploration of issues related to polluted soils, providing insights into innovative strategies for remediation and environmental restoration (Brillas, 2021; Cappuyns, 2013; Hu et al., 2021; Li et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2021). It covers various dimensions of soil pollution and soil quality, including bioavailability, bioaccumulation, nutrients, organic carbon, and solid waste (Soobhany, 2019). Specific contaminants such as cadmium, lead, and greenhouse gases highlight a focus on understanding the environmental implications of soil pollution (Amponsah et al., 2018; Cai et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2020b; Gan et al., 2019; Hussain et al., 2021; Shakoor et al., 2021a,b,c,d). The cluster also reflects the impact of human and industrial activities on heavy metal contamination in soils (Zhou and Wang, 2019). Innovative solutions like biofuel, compost, hydrochar, and hydrothermal carbonization signify a commitment to sustainable soil management (Alagić et al., 2015; Ventorino et al., 2019). Terms like rare earth elements, potassium, and phytoremediation emphasize diverse strategies for addressing soil contamination (Chen et al., 2020c; Dong et al., 2021; Grobelak et al., 2017; Luo et al., 2016; Oprčkal et al., 2020; Shah and Daverey, 2021; Wang et al., 2019). This cluster suggests a multidisciplinary approach by encompassing concepts such as life cycle analysis, health risk assessment, and economic benefit (Hou et al., 2017; Kuppens et al., 2015). Additionally, global addressing of this cluster’s theme is showcased through examples from countries like Brazil, Nigeria, and Romania. In short, the cluster provides a nuanced perspective on the challenges of soil contamination and diverse approaches to remediation and sustainable soil management.

• **Cluster A3 (35 words): Soil Contamination and Washing**

This distinct cluster delves into the interplay among surfactants, soils, washing, and detergency, offering insights into soil washing and detergency methodologies. The cluster is primarily centered on comprehending soil removal techniques, particularly from textile substrates, as indicated by the prevalence of keywords such as anionic surfactants, foam washing, and kinetics within the cluster’s literature (Oya, 2007; Oya and Minagawa, 1989; Sato et al., 1988a,b). Furthermore, the cluster explores the ramifications of detergent usage and laundering activities on soil dynamics, underscoring terms such as detergency, detergents, and laundering (Cunliffe et al., 1988). This emphasis is exemplified through investigations comparing various detergent formulations, and assessing their efficacy in soil removal, soil re-deposition, and calcium carbonate deposition (Kim et al., 1987). Moreover, the incorporation of biopolymers, enzymes, and proteases within the cluster’s discourse signifies a concerted inquiry into enzyme-based detergents tailored for foam washing applications (Sato et al., 1989). Additionally, the inclusion of artificial soil, carbon black, and zeolite underscores the diverse array of materials under scrutiny within soil washing studies (Sato et al., 1985). Soil washing, heavy metal decontamination, and the removal of oil and toxic elements from contaminated soil and wastewater, along with corresponding techniques, represent another line of research within this older cluster, which appears to be more recent (Boente et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2021; Kim and Baek, 2019; Li et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2018; Wei et al., 2022). Notably, the cluster’s interdisciplinary approach amalgamates principles from soil science, chemistry, and engineering domains, facilitating an elucidation of the mechanisms governing soil removal and washing processes.

• **Cluster A4 (26 words): Soil-Water Contamination and Technical Efficiencies**

This cluster revolves around heavy metal contamination, irrigation and groundwater dynamics by exploring the nuanced dynamics of soil-

water contamination aspects (Hanson et al., 2006; Worqlul et al., 2017). The term adsorption signifies an investigation into materials like Biochar, which offer extensive potential for applications spanning wastewater treatment, soil fertility enhancement, and environmental remediation efforts (Dai et al., 2020; Pandey et al., 2020; Wang and Wang (2019a)). Moreover, the inclusion of factors such as global warming potential underscores the importance of an environmental perspective in studies concerning adsorption phenomena, irrigation methodologies, and agricultural practices (Chen et al., 2017; Li et al., 2020). The cluster explores technology adoption and the implementation of advanced techniques to facilitate more intelligent irrigation practices (Benyezza et al., 2021a,b; Krishnan et al., 2020a,b; Mérida García et al., 2018a,b). In summary, this cluster provides an exploration of contamination and efficiency intricacies within the soil-water context. It encompasses various aspects ranging from traditional irrigation methods to innovative technologies, and from the application of organic materials to soil, water, and environmental remediation efforts.

3.2.2.1.2. *Overarching Cluster B: Life Cycle and Environmental Impact*

• **Cluster B1 (47 words): Emissions, Global Warming, and (Agro) forestry**

The fourth identified group of keywords within the context of soil addresses environmental challenges such as greenhouse gases, heavy metal pollution, nitrogen pollution, and global warming, with a specific focus on emissions and agroforestry (Bong et al., 2017; Biswas et al., 2010a; Cai et al., 2018; Chu et al., 2019; Costa et al., 2018a,b; Eldesouky et al., 2018; Guardia et al., 2019; Nahed-Toral et al., 2013; Shakoor et al., 2021a,b,c,d; Shan et al., 2021a,b; Utomo et al., 2016). The cluster suggests the importance of realizing nitrogen dynamics and greenhouse gas contributions, showcasing terms such as N₂O emission, denitrification, and nitrogen removal, among others (Lu et al., 2016; Shan et al., 2021a,b; Xiang et al., 2015; Xiao et al., 2019; Ying et al., 2017). The inclusion of keywords like soil temperature, precipitation, and vegetation density (Peng et al., 2019), further highlights the focus of this cluster on environmental impacts. Moreover, the appearance of economic analysis, life cycle inventory, and meta-analysis indicates a multidisciplinary approach that incorporates both scientific and economic perspectives (Amiri et al., 2019; Noorollahi et al., 2016; Shakoor et al., 2021a,b,c,d). Beyond all, the recognition of examples from various regions, such as China and Iran, signals the global nature of these issues (Chu et al., 2019).

• **Cluster B2 (29 words): Life Cycle Assessment and Carbon Footprint**

The cluster focusing on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Environmental Impact delves into the intricacies of assessing environmental considerations and the overall life cycle of soil-related activities. LCA serves as a pivotal tool within this domain, enabling researchers to discern which choices offer the most favourable environmental performance, as evidenced by studies (Arvidsson et al., 2011; Knudsen et al., 2014; Mattsson et al., 2000; Meisterling et al., 2009; Niero et al., 2014; Saer et al., 2013a,b; Segheta et al., 2016; Silalertruksa et al., 2017a,b). The cluster meticulously examines the environmental ramifications of various factors, including but not limited to carbon footprint, fertilizer usage, nonpoint source pollution, and soil carbon sequestration, as underscored by relevant research (Knudsen et al., 2014; Matusčík et al., 2020a,b; Petersen et al., 2013; Yang et al., 2014; Zhou et al., 2019). Furthermore, the cluster demonstrates a commitment to addressing uncertainties inherent in different strategies through the integration of LCA with techniques such as Monte Carlo simulation and sensitivity analysis, as outlined in studies (Niero et al., 2014). Climate change and mitigation emerge as pivotal focal points within this cluster, emphasizing the imperative for sustainable approaches to soil-related activities

and agricultural practices, as elucidated by pertinent research (Partey et al., 2018; Segheta et al., 2016). In summary, the LCA and Carbon Footprint cluster employs methodologies like LCA to optimize environmental performance in soil management. It addresses uncertainties and emphasizes climate change mitigation for sustainable agricultural practices.

3.2.2.1.3. *Overarching Cluster C: Sustainability and Ecosystems.*

• **Cluster C1 (65 words): Environmental Monitoring and Land Use Management**

This cluster is shaped based on the complex dynamics of land use, change detection, deforestation, urbanization, soil erosion, and their impact on environmental health. Specifically, it maps a multi-faceted examination of topics including land use, land cover change, deforestation, remote sensing, soil erosion, and soil and water conservation. With keywords ranging from air pollution to watershed, this cluster represents the intricate relationships between land use, natural resources, and environmental impacts (Castanheira and Freire, 2013; Roy et al., 2020a,b). Terms such as deforestation, land use change, erosion, and soil degradation highlight the environmental challenges addressed (Nunes et al., 2011), while the appearance of GIS (geographic information system), remote sensing, and modelling shows the importance of advanced technologies in monitoring and managing land resources (Abd El-Kawy et al., 2011; Al-Adamat et al., 2003; Chomitz and Gray, 2017; Courault et al., 2005; Dixon, 2005a,b; Rahman, 2008a,b). Moreover, research in this cluster delves into issues like climate change, soil and water conservation, ecosystem services, and environmental management, emphasizing a commitment to addressing sustainability challenges on land and water uses (Desta et al., 2017; Gao et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2019).

• **Cluster C2 (43 words): Waste Management and Resource Recovery**

The thematic focus within cluster C2 becomes evident through identifying keywords, indicating a concentration on various aspects of waste management. This entails the meticulous handling and disposal of diverse waste types, exemplified by terms such as activated carbon, anaerobic digestion, biochar, composting, pyrolysis, and vermicomposting (Bustamante et al., 2013; Chandra and Bhattacharya, 2019; Ghodake et al., 2021; Li et al., 2019; Shan et al., 2021a,b; Shukla et al., 2019; Wang and Wang (2019a)). Additionally, the cluster broadens its scope to include recycling and remediation, incorporating keywords like fertilization, GHG emission, life cycle impact assessment, recycle, remediation, and reuse (Du et al., 2018; Matušík et al., 2020a,b; Saer et al., 2013a,b; Singh et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2019a,b). This underscores a holistic approach to soil and water waste management, emphasizing the importance of mitigating environmental impact while optimizing resource utilization. Going beyond the realm of waste treatment, the cluster delves into the investigation of environmental and health risks associated with diverse waste management practices (Disfani et al., 2012a,b,c; Wu et al., 2016a,b). Principal considerations encompass heavy metals, shedding light on ecological and health risks, thus highlighting the imperative for sustainable waste management solutions that prioritize both environmental and human health (Adebeye et al., 2020a,b,c; Han et al., 2020a,b; Li et al., 2019; Orlins and Guan, 2016; Xu et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2016a,b). On the whole, the group's exploration transcends conventional waste disposal practices, acknowledging the multifaceted challenges and opportunities intrinsic to the domain of waste management within the context of soil.

• **Cluster C3 (12 words): Mining Operations and Ecosystem Health**

The cluster C3 serves as a supplementary component to both the

initial cluster titled "Soil Stabilization, Construction Materials, and Recycling" and the C2 cluster designated "Waste Management and Resource Recovery". At the core of this cluster lies a focal point on mining and construction operations, waste management, (constructed) wetlands, and environmental sustainability. This emphasis is evident through terminologies such as construction and demolition waste, wastewater, bottom ash, and copper, as referenced in several studies (Celauro et al., 2017; Deng et al., 2021; Reyes-Bozo et al., 2014; Saumya et al., 2015; Vieira et al., 2016a,b). Notably, the cluster underscores research themes including the remediation of contaminated mining soil (Reyes-Bozo et al., 2014) and the assessment of soil erosion predictions originating from waste dumps of opencast mines and their ensuing environmental impacts (Yellishetty et al., 2013). Furthermore, the inclusion of concepts such as environmental sustainability, impact assessment, and resilience highlights an outlook that integrates environmental considerations into construction practices and waste management (Agarwal et al., 2022; Yellishetty et al., 2013). In summary, this cluster represents an investigation into sustainable mining and construction solutions, waste treatment within wetland ecosystems, and their associated environmental ramifications, drawing attention to the imperative for conscientious soil and environmental stewardship across varied contexts.

• **Cluster C4 (42 words): Ecological Economics**

This thematic cluster within the soil context encompasses a wide range of subjects including ecosystem, nature-based solutions, agroecology, production, urban agriculture, consumer behavior, risk management, environmental policy, and sustainable development. These terms mainly highlight the cluster's focus on addressing ecological and economic balance and mitigating deleterious impacts (Biswas et al., 2010; Costa et al., 2018a,b; Gastauer et al., 2018; Han et al., 2020a,b; He et al., 2018; Lal et al., 2019a,b; Li et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2019a,b; Lin et al., 2020; Partey et al., 2018; Paul et al., 2019; Shakoor et al., 2021a,b,c,d; Wan et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2021; Xue et al., 2022). Within the broader theme, investigations are conducted into the impacts of climate change on agricultural productivity and the wider environmental impacts of agricultural production, spanning diverse geographical regions, including Australia and Vietnam (Biswas et al., 2010; Kontgis et al., 2019). On the same note, the inclusion of terms such as construction equipment, construction management, and industrial waste indicates the significance of systemic approaches to sustainable development (de Azevedo et al., 2018; Fortunato III et al., 2012; Hossain et al., 2020; Li and Chen, 2020; Li et al., 2016; Magnusson et al., 2015; Harjani et al., 2017; Ramos et al., 2017; Vieira et al., 2016a,b). In addition, terms like evaluation and risk management underline the cluster's commitment to addressing externalities and potential risks associated with diverse practices (Disfani et al., 2012a,b,c; Li and Wang, 2019). In short, this cluster addresses the intricate dimensions of ecological economics and sustainable development within the context of soil.

3.2.2.1.4. *Overarching Cluster D: agricultural practices and efficiency.*

• **Cluster D1 (37 words): Innovative Agricultural Techniques and Use Efficiency**

Similar to cluster A4, this cluster in the context of soil and agriculture chiefly focuses on groundwater resources, drainage, and water use efficiency. The application of tools like Ansys, finite element method, and the artificial neural network indicates a commitment to researching advanced mathematical modelling concerning soil and water (Meesawasd et al., 2016). Several methods and tools are used to enhance water management in terms of quality, use efficiency, and sustainability. Crucial terms in this group of keywords like groundwater (Aredes et al., 2012; Dixon, 2005a,b; Herath et al., 2013; Ibrakhimov et al., 2007; Rahman, 2008a,b; Zhang et al., 2021), drainage (Ayars et al., 1999;

Kefeni et al., 2017; Ko et al., 2015; Oster and Grattan, 2002), water use efficiency (Capra and Scicolone, 2007; Laura et al., 2020; Oster and Grattan, 2002; Ren et al., 2017), uncertainty (D'Ambrosio et al., 2020; Ren et al., 2017), and modelling/simulation (Alamdari and Sample, 2019; Geng and Sharpley, 2019; Ren et al., 2017; Srinivas et al., 2020) represent studies that investigate groundwater vulnerability, pollution removal, water footprint assessment, watershed restoration, water reuse, water-saving irrigation, sewage sludge treatment, and acid mine drainage. The consideration of factors such as ammonia volatilization, nitrate leaching, and water quality points towards an approach that addresses environmental concerns (Chen et al., 2021; Li et al., 2017). Additionally, keywords such as crop yield, cropping systems, and nutrient cycling highlight the orientation of this cluster towards optimizing agricultural cleaner production and sustainability. Overall, this cluster represents a comprehensive exploration of soil-related water management in terms of quality, use efficiency, and sustainable agriculture.

• **Cluster D2 (36 words): Sustainable Agriculture and Food Security**

Strongly linked to the cluster C4, the theme of this group of keywords showcases a holistic perspective regarding sustainability, incorporating economic and social effects. Concepts such as circular economy, Emergency, food security, and organic agriculture underscore the focus of this cluster on environmentally friendly practices and sustainable agriculture (Adegbeye et al., 2020a,b,c; Antoniou et al., 2019; Conde-Cid et al., 2018; D'Emden et al., 2006a,b; Garai and Sarkar, 2022; Kassie et al., 2013a,b; Notarnicola et al., 2012a,b; Salomon and Cavagnaro, 2022; Valdivia and Barbieri, 2014; Xie et al., 2021). The inclusion of climate change adaptation, drought, and salinity points towards addressing challenges posed by environmental variations (Partey et al., 2018; Roy et al., 2020a,b; Wang and Dai, 2020). In addition, environmental and (socio-) economic assessment of sustainability-oriented practices and recycling appears to be another research theme within this cluster (Dolman et al., 2014; Krol-Badziak et al., 2021; Lahlou et al., 2021; Rashid et al., 2023). Keywords like AHP (analytic hierarchy process), multi-criteria analysis, TOPSIS, and geographic information systems highlight a commitment to structured decision-making, promoting sustainable innovation, efficiency, and soil and water conservation (Krois and Schulte, 2014; Ramya and Devadas, 2019; Wang et al., 2019). Moreover, the appearance of keywords such as farmers, Africa, Pakistan, and Thailand suggests the promising role of sustainable farming and agricultural practices in addressing hunger, reducing poverty, achieving food security, and improving nutrition as well as social standards in particular in low-middle-income countries (Adegbeye et al., 2020a,b,c; Hinge et al., 2021; Kassie et al., 2013a,b; Mutenje et al., 2016; Partey et al., 2018; Pongpat et al., 2017; Silalertruksa et al., 2017a,b). This cluster within the context of soil contributes to shaping the future of sustainable agriculture and meeting global sustainable development goals.

• **Cluster D3 (58 words): Soil Health, Agricultural Productivity, and Profitability**

This thematic cluster delves into the intricate dimensions of soil health, crop productivity, and profitability within soil scholarly discourse. Adoption, biodiversity, and crop production are included terms that underline the intricate nature of agricultural practices (D'Emden et al., 2006a,b; Guan et al., 2020, 2006; Kassie et al., 2013a,b; Li et al., 2020). In tandem, biofertilizer, organic, and nutrient recovery signify a steadfast commitment to ecologically sustainable farming processes and practices (Adegbeye et al., 2020a,b,c; Zhang et al., 2020). On the same note, this cluster explores soil health intricacies through terms like soil carbon, soil fertility, and soil analysis, reflecting a dedicated focus on optimizing soil conditions for enhanced crop productivity

and sustainable impacts (Bekchanov and Mirzabaev, 2018; Jia et al., 2022; Lal et al., 2019a,b; Shakoor et al., 2021a,b,c,d). Comprehensive insights into driving factors, growth, sustainable agriculture, and profitability showcase a better understanding of the linkage between soil health and agricultural productivity (Banson et al., 2016; Hernandez-Aguilera et al., 2018; Li et al., 2020; Min et al., 2021). The reflection of food safety, pollution, and wastewater treatment within this context signals the wider implications of agricultural practices on both environmental integrity and human health (Notarnicola et al., 2012a,b; Van Der Werf et al., 2014; Zhan et al., 2019). In essence, this cluster provides a nuanced and integrated perspective on the confluence of soil health, sustainable agriculture, productivity, and profitability, synthesizing a comprehensive understanding of their interconnected dimensions.

• **Cluster D4 (55 words): Data Mining and Technology in Agriculture**

The D4 soil-based thematic cluster is oriented towards the integration of advanced technologies and data-driven approaches into the domain of agricultural practices. Several detected keywords in this group, including big data, data mining, and machine learning, underscore a steadfast emphasis on the strategic application of technology for decision-making in agriculture (Kumar et al., 2015). Additionally, key descriptors such as automation, artificial intelligence, and the Internet of Things (IoT) further highlight the cluster's concentration on spearheading technological innovations (Krishnan et al., 2020a,b; Yanes et al., 2020). Precision agriculture plays a significant role in this research area with keywords like precision agriculture, smart farming, and smart irrigation, indicating a move towards more efficient and resource-conscious farming processes and practices (Aubert et al., 2012a,b; Beneyza et al., 2021a,b; Partey et al., 2018). Furthermore, the incorporation of terms such as drip irrigation, energy efficiency, and solar energy amplifies the cluster's link to the development of sustainable and environmentally friendly agricultural technologies (Capra and Scicolone, 2007b; García et al., 2018a,b). In addition, the cluster engages in an exploration of sensor-based and monitoring techniques, exemplified by the utilization of soil moisture sensors and NDVI, for real-time data collection and analysis (Chen et al., 2011; Kumar et al., 2015). Briefly, this cluster provides comprehensive insights into the transformative role of technology in the contemporization and optimization of agricultural practices, shedding light on the integration of sustainable farming practices with cutting-edge technological advancements.

• **Cluster D5 (21 words): Nanotechnology in Sustainable Agriculture**

The final group of keywords identified in this review embodies an exploration of radical advancements within BMA-related soil research. It explicitly stresses the incorporation of nanotechnology innovations into agricultural practices. Terms such as nano fertilizers, nanomaterials, nanoparticles, nano pesticides, and nanosensors portray the key research scope within this cluster (Liu et al., 2019a,b; Rai et al., 2023; Rashid et al., 2023; Shaghaleh et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2023; Zhou et al., 2022). These concepts collectively feature efforts toward harnessing nanoscale technologies to improve organic and sustainable farming practices. Additionally, concepts such as efficiency and nutrient use efficiency emphasize the importance of nanotechnologies and their role in increasing agricultural efficiency. By taking the potential benefits and safety concerns of using nanotechnology into account, the cluster underlines the improvement of nitrogen use efficiency and the reduction of non-point source pollution in agriculture (Wang et al., 2023). Representative studies also demonstrate that sub-surface drip irrigation using micro-nano bubble-enriched water significantly increases crop yield, water use efficiency, and fruit quality by improving soil oxygen levels and beneficial bacterial activity (Liu et al.,

2019a,b; Zhou et al., 2022)). In summary, the cluster addresses enhancements in sustainable agriculture with a specific emphasis on the application of nanotechnologies, nano-fertilizers, nano-sensors, and nanomaterials.

These thematic clusters described above not only provide a more detailed perspective on the research landscape within BMA-related soil studies but also establish connections with the broader overarching clusters identified in the earlier analysis. The interdisciplinary nature of these clusters underlies the complexity and diversity of research in this field, spanning environmental management, agriculture, technology, waste management, ecosystems, and sustainability.

3.2.2.2. Overlay visualization: unveiling temporal trends. To enhance our understanding of thematic evolution within the soil literature, we delve into the temporal dynamics of pivotal concepts through the Authors-Keyword overlay visualization network, depicted in Fig. 8 (also referenced in Fig. 7). This analysis complements and extends the insights gleaned from our earlier overlay examination of All-Keyword analysis. By scrutinizing this network, we aim to elucidate emerging trends alongside enduring themes. This odyssey traverses a considerable span, notably from the years 1980–2023, encapsulating the interplay between pioneering ideas and contemporary research trajectories.

By juxtaposing emerging frontiers with enduring paradigms, this analysis provides insights that not only enrich our understanding of thematic shifts but also guide future exploration, illuminating the dynamic contours of research within the interdisciplinary realm of soil management.

As the most recent thematic group, cluster D5, Nanotechnology in Sustainable Agriculture, is characterized by terms primarily appearing

in a light yellow colour. This cluster heralds the integration of nanotechnology into soil management practices, harnessing nanoscale technologies to augment nutrient delivery, pest control, and sensing capabilities within soil systems, thereby fostering sustainable soil management and organic farming. Noteworthy terms such as nano fertilizers, nanomaterials, nanoparticles, nano pesticides, and nanosensors, all bearing an APY of 2022, stand as vivid testaments to recent advancements in scholarly discourse.

Similarly, Cluster D4, Data Mining and Technology in Agriculture illuminated in light yellow, serves as a compelling testament to the strategic amalgamation of advanced technologies into agricultural practices. Salient terms such as smart farming, machine learning, deep learning, Internet of Things (IoT), humidity sensor, soil moisture sensor, artificial intelligence, and image processing, spanning an APY range from 2019 to 2021, epitomize a dynamic landscape where technology assumes a pivotal role in decision-making, precision agriculture, and the formulation of sustainable farming processes.

Compared to emerging clusters, cluster A3, Soil Contamination and Washing displayed in regal purple, stands out as an old bastion of soil literature. This cluster, adorned with terms such as cotton fabrics, detergents, soil removal, surfactants, enzymes, washing, and laundering, unfurls the intricate tapestry of soil contamination, washing, and remediation. Anchored by an APY dating back to the 1980s, these terms embody the foundational principles that have steadfastly underpinned soil research over successive decades (till the 2010s), resonating as timeless pillars within the scholarly domain.

Interconnected terms like soil health (APY: 2020) and agricultural productivity (APY: 2020) in Cluster D3 extend beyond their specific cluster, linking to broader environmental concerns such as carbon sequestration (APY: 2019) in Cluster B1 and climate change (APY: 2019)

Fig. 8. Overlay visualization of authors' keywords (Constructed via VOSviewer v.1.6.20 for the sample N = 6,910, f (frequency) > 5 → 636 keywords).

represent more recent or emerging themes. The temporal progression of the overarching clusters is additionally illustrated by a curved arrow that moves from foundational to contemporary themes.

While the thematic clusters are nested within these four overarching clusters, a higher-order synthesis reveals two key domains that encompass the entire body of literature. These two domains — (1) **Soil Health, Environmental, and Technical Management** and (2) **Circular Economy, Ecosystem Services, and Sustainable Development** — represent the most integrative level of analysis. They serve as conceptual anchors that help interpret the diversity of topics covered and illustrate how soil is increasingly embedded in both technical operations and broader sustainability and organizational contexts. The discussion that follows builds on this labeling logic to explore the interdisciplinary relationships across soil functions, ecosystem services, SDGs, and BMA concepts reflected in the identified clusters.

4.1.1. Soil health, environmental, and Technical Management

The research concern about healthy and less polluted soils pervades across the clusters and resonates with SDGs, including zero hunger, clean water and sanitation, climate action, and biodiversity conservation (Das et al., 2022).

The review emphasizes the critical issues associated with soil pollution (Cluster A2), highlighting heavy metals such as arsenic, cadmium, chromium, mercury, lead, copper, zinc, and nickel (Zhao et al., 2022), as well as nitrogen oxide and gas emissions (Cluster B1) (Lu et al., 2021; Oertel et al., 2016). It also draws attention to established research paths, including soil washing, and the extraction of oil and toxic elements from contaminated soil and wastewater, as documented in clusters A3 and A4, which significantly contribute to tackling soil contamination challenges.

Soil pollution and soil health are implicitly related as soil pollution directly affects soil health (Shahane and Shivay, 2021). Various sources of soil pollution have diverse impacts on soil health. Soil properties like porosity and nutrient levels can be significantly altered due to pollution from industrial waste or sewage sludge, leading to the accumulation of harmful heavy metals (Shahane and Shivay, 2021; Zhou and Wang, 2019). These contaminants pose risks to human health through bioaccumulation and contribute to groundwater and surface water pollution, jeopardizing aquatic life and water safety (highlighted in clusters A2 and A4). Moreover, soil pollution impedes crop germination and growth, disrupts soil microorganism populations, and in severe cases renders soil unsuitable for cultivation (Shahane and Shivay, 2021). As reflected in Cluster D, persistent pollutants like heavy metals further exacerbate the challenge, posing hurdles to sustainable agricultural practices, including organic farming and the direct use of nutrient-containing minerals (Shahane and Shivay, 2021).

Specified in cluster A2, an urgent need appears to face soil pollution and implement effective remediation strategies to reduce environmental and health risks (Xu et al., 2021). Addressing soil pollution requires comprehensive strategies aimed at preventing pollution, mitigating its impacts, and promoting sustainable soil management practices to preserve soil health for future generations (Lehmann et al., 2020).

The benefits of soil health management practices (SHMPs) are underlined by several studies, particularly within the agricultural context (Cluster D) (Hopwood et al., 2021; Khangura et al., 2023; Lehmann et al., 2020; Stevens, 2018). The improvement of these practices plays a significant role in boosting soil function and resilience (Carlisle, 2016). In addition, SHMPs foster soil fertility and structure and contribute to carbon sequestration, water infiltration, and biodiversity conservation (USDA NRCS, 2018).

Aligned with the research trajectory of cluster D3, Hopwood et al. (2021) outline a set of key actions forming the foundation of Sustainable SHMPs, applicable across diverse agricultural contexts. These actions emphasize the imperative to protect soil health through targeted strategies. First and foremost, minimizing erosion risk stands as a priority, achieved through the implementation of conservation systems that

shield crop fields from erosive forces caused by wind and water runoff. Moreover, the maintenance of year-round soil cover or continuous living root systems is advocated to mitigate erosion and enhance soil stability. Concurrently, the reduction of mechanical cultivation and compaction is highlighted to preserve soil structure and minimize soil disturbance.

In tandem with these practices, augmenting organic matter content through natural inputs, while simultaneously diminishing reliance on synthetic fertilizers, emerges as a pivotal strategy for nurturing soil health and fertility (Tuomisto et al., 2012). Additionally, maximizing crop diversity is underscored as a means of promoting soil resilience and ecological balance. Integration of crops and livestock further amplifies soil health benefits, whether through rotational schemes or the incorporation of cover crops into grazing systems. Finally, to bolster soil biodiversity, Hopwood et al. (2021) advocate for the reduction or elimination of pesticide usage, including soil fumigants, thus fostering a conducive environment for soil organisms crucial to ecosystem functioning. Together, these key actions capture a holistic approach to soil management aimed at preserving and enhancing soil health for sustainable agricultural production, all while harvesting better profits and often better yields (USDA NRCS, 2018).

Moreover, incorporating crop residue and agro-industrial waste is integral in enhancing soil health by augmenting organic matter content and nutrient levels, thereby promoting nutrient retention and microbial activity. A research emphasis has been placed on managing and disposing of diverse waste types, as evidenced by terms such as activated carbon, anaerobic digestion, biochar, composting, pyrolysis, and vermicomposting, detected in cluster C2. The literature features the widespread adoption of soil amendments like biochar and compost to improve soil health (Kavitha et al., 2018; Puga et al., 2015; Shaaban et al., 2018). Biochar, particularly, has emerged as a promising tool with multiple benefits, including slow-release nutrient supply, carbon sequestration for climate change mitigation, and reduction of soil contaminant leaching and bioavailability (Hou, 2023; Majumder et al., 2019). Composting similarly enriches soil fertility by converting organic waste into nutrient-rich compost, promoting healthy plant growth (Ayilara et al., 2020).

Further, agroforestry practices and systems have been promoted for decades (cluster B1) as they can enrich soil organic carbon better than monocropping systems, improve soil nutrient availability and soil fertility due to the presence of trees in the system, and enhance soil microbial dynamics, which would positively influence soil health (Dollinger and Jose, 2018). By integrating biochar, composting, and soil amendments alongside agroforestry practices, holistic soil management approaches are employed to promote sustainable agriculture and environmental resilience, emphasizing the interconnectedness of soil health with overall ecosystem vitality (Dollinger and Jose, 2018).

On the same note, transitioning from agricultural contexts to urban environments, nature-based solutions are increasingly recognized as effective tools for mitigating soil degradation and promoting environmental resilience. These solutions including wetlands and street trees (cluster B1) offer cost-effective approaches to urban soil management while providing multiple benefits for ecosystems and human well-being (Evans et al., 2022). Additionally, Technosols constructed from city waste contribute to circular economies while providing ecosystem services (Evans et al., 2022).

Despite agriculture's primary focus in the literature reviewed, there is a growing recognition of soil health's broader implications in sustaining ecosystems and supporting human activities across multiple sectors (Zalesny et al., 2021). The influence of soil health extends beyond agriculture to various sectors such as construction, mining, and urbanization, as evidenced by several clusters of the present review (i.e., A1, C2, and C3). In construction, soil health directly affects the stability and durability of structures, while in mining, it plays a crucial role in land reclamation efforts and ecosystem restoration. Terms like fly ash, embankment, erosion control, and geotechnical properties highlight the importance of environmental considerations and emphasize the role of

reinforced soil and recycled waste in sustainable construction practices. Furthermore, research on soil-structure interaction, mechanical properties, and remediation underscores the significance of soil quality and health across diverse applications.

The emergence of the most recent cluster, Agricultural Practices and Efficiency (Cluster D), signifies growing research interest in areas such as precision agriculture, use efficiencies, advanced decision-making methods, nanotechnology applications, and data mining and artificial intelligence tools. This emerging theme, along with Cluster B (i.e., Life Cycle and Environmental Impact), offers innovative approaches to enhancing agricultural productivity, optimizing resource use efficiency, facilitating organic farming, improving food security, reducing environmental footprints, making informed decisions and designing effective mitigation strategies to minimize environmental degradation (Abbate et al., 2023).

In the context of agricultural innovation, precision agriculture, exemplified by concepts such as smart farming and smart irrigation (in cluster D4), emerges as a prominent theme in the literature, signalling a shift towards more efficient and resource-conscious farming practices (Aubert et al., 2012a,b; Benyezza et al., 2021a,b; Pereira et al., 2018). Likewise, integrating nanoscale technologies into agriculture, reflected in terms such as nano fertilizers, nanomaterials, nanoparticles, nano pesticides, and nanosensors, underscores efforts to enhance organic and sustainable farming practices. These advancements are particularly focused on improving nutrient use efficiency, pest management, and soil and water sensing capabilities, while also enhancing crop nitrogen use efficiencies (Wang et al., 2023).

Furthermore, nutrient management techniques emerge as integral components of SHMPs, crucial for ensuring optimal nutrient availability for crops while mitigating adverse environmental impacts like nutrient runoff and leaching (Paramesh et al., 2023). Notably, incorporating nanotechnology advancements into agricultural practices, as emphasized in cluster D5 identified in this review, plays a key role in maintaining nutrient balance, reducing pollution, and enhancing soil fertility. These findings collectively highlight the evolving landscape of agricultural practices towards sustainability and efficiency through the integration of precision agriculture and nanotechnology (Duhan et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2021). Moreover, studies on sustainable waste and water management, recycling, and circular economy principles further stress the necessity of embedding ecological principles within SHMPs.

4.1.2. Circular economy, ecosystem services and sustainable development

Drawing upon the insights gleaned from the network analysis of co-occurring keywords in the literature, it becomes evident that the concept of "Sustainable Development" occupies a central and interconnected position within the discourse on soil and management. This centrality is vividly depicted in Fig. 5 and covered in cluster C4 where "Sustainable Development" serves as a critical nexus intricately linked to various thematic elements across clusters. These connections illustrate the depth and breadth of the influence of "Sustainable Development," highlighting its pivotal role in bridging multiple domains within the literature. Whether shaping agricultural practices, driving technological innovations, or informing environmental impact assessments, "Sustainable Development" emerges as a linchpin that connects various facets of research and discourse, showing its critical importance in guiding future directions for soil health and ecosystem services research (Bouma, 2014; Martinho, 2019; Montanarella and Panagos, 2021).

The findings, prominently illustrated in cluster C4 focusing on Sustainability and Circular Economy, provide a comprehensive view of sustainability, integrating economic and social dimensions. It emphasizes environmentally friendly practices and sustainable agriculture, addressing challenges posed by environmental variations. The central theme underscores sustainability management in relation to soil, emphasizing the significance of structured decision-making tools and technologies for promoting sustainable innovation and efficiency. Research in this realm significantly shapes the future of sustainable

agriculture, aligning closely with global sustainable development goals.

The concept of circular economy emerges as a framework for advancing soil health and sustainability management practices, emphasizing the retention of materials within productive use while minimizing waste generation and environmental pollution. The circular economy model offers a pathway towards sustainable resource management by reshaping business and economic systems to eliminate waste and repair previous damage. Integrating circular economy principles into business models impacts internal operations and fosters collaboration along the supply chain, with practices such as product leasing gaining prominence (Spooren et al., 2020). However, transitioning to a circular business model requires adapting existing economic models to ensure economic viability, particularly in resource recovery processes such as enhanced landfill mining (Cluster A1) and urban mining (Spooren et al., 2020). While the environmental benefits of resource recovery are clear, the economic feasibility hinges on various factors such as technological advancements, market dynamics, and regulatory frameworks. Therefore, a thorough analysis of site-specific characteristics and economic factors is essential to inform decision-making regarding resource recovery initiatives within the context of soil and sustainability management (Spooren et al., 2020).

In the same vein, the exploration of waste management and resource recovery in the literature reveals the importance of sustainable waste disposal practices and efficient resource utilization (Cluster C2). This encompasses addressing diverse waste types, recycling, remediation, and investigating associated environmental and health risks. Complementing this, the focus on mining and construction operations, waste management, constructed wetlands, and environmental sustainability accentuates the imperative of sustainable practices in these industries and their broader implications for soil and environmental stewardship (Clusters A1 and C3).

Further, as reflected in cluster D1, examining water management, including groundwater resources, drainage, and water use efficiency, underscores the significance of enhancing water quality, efficiency, and overall sustainability, promoting cleaner agricultural production practices. Additionally, highlighted in Cluster C1, the dynamics of land use, change detection, deforestation, and soil erosion emphasize the intricate relationship between human activities and environmental health, with considerations of land cover change, soil and water conservation, and ecosystem services.

4.2. Bridging soil functions, sustainability goals, and management approaches

Building on the thematic clusters identified and the two overarching research domains that permeate them, a clearer picture emerges of how soil, as a form of natural capital, sits at the intersection of ecosystem services, the SDGs, and BMA concepts. The literature reveals a multi-layered, interdisciplinary landscape in which soil is no longer regarded in isolation or merely as a biophysical substrate. Instead, it is increasingly recognized as a foundational infrastructure for enabling sustainability transitions across diverse sectors, most notably agriculture and food systems, but also extending to mining, construction, and waste management.

As summarized in Table 3, each cluster demonstrates a specific constellation of soil's interactions with other natural capitals (such as water, atmosphere, and biodiversity), as well as their alignment with corresponding ecosystem services and key SDGs. Regulating services such as climate mitigation, water purification, and erosion control are especially prevalent, followed by provisioning services like food production and nutrient supply. Supporting services (e.g., nutrient cycling and habitat maintenance) are often embedded within broader environmental outcomes, while cultural services, though recognized in a few clusters, remain comparatively underexplored.

Research emphasizes the importance of maintaining soil health and underscores its integral connection to ecosystem services (Kosanic and

Table 3
Integrative summary of thematic clusters linking soil themes with natural capital interdependencies, ecosystem services, SDGs, and management approaches.

Thematic Cluster (Interdependent Natural Capitals)	Linked Ecosystem Services	SDGs	BMA (Interdisciplinary) Concepts, Methods, Tools & Approaches
A1: Soil Stabilization, Construction Materials, and Environmental Protection <i>Soil ⇌ Mineral/rock resources & landform stability (with secondary links to water via erosion control)</i>	*Erosion & landslide control (Regulating) *Load-bearing/slope-stability support for infrastructure (Supporting) *Secondary raw materials from recycled soil/fly-ash (Provisioning)	SDG 9; SDG 11; SDG 12; SDG 15	– (BMA gap)
A2: Soil Pollution and Remediation Techniques <i>Soil ⇌ Water quality & aquatic systems; Soil ⇌ Atmosphere (GHG mitigation); Soil ⇌ Biodiversity</i>	*Detoxification/pollutant attenuation & water purification (Regulating) *Recovery of soil quality & nutrient cycling (Supporting) *GHG-mitigation co-benefit from cleaner soils (Regulating)	SDG 3; SDG 6; SDG 12; SDG 13; SDG 15	LCA; Health risk assessment; Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA); Economic cost–benefit evaluation
A3: Soil Contamination and Washing <i>Soil ⇌ Water (industrial/wash-water effluents)</i>	*Removal of oils, heavy metals, surfactants from soils & effluents (Regulating) *Restored soil functionality post-washing (Supporting)	SDG 3; SDG 6; SDG 11; SDG 12	– (BMA gap)
A4: Soil–Water Contamination and Technical Efficiencies <i>Soil ⇌ Ground- & irrigation-water resources; Soil ⇌ Climate (via global-warming-potential metrics)</i>	*Heavy-metal adsorption & water-quality protection (Regulating) *Soil-water retention & fertility enhancement (biochar, irrigation tech) (Supporting) *Supply of cleaner irrigation water to crops (Provisioning)	SDG 2; SDG 3; SDG 6; SDG 13; SDG 15	Technical-efficiency analysis; Technology-adoption studies; ANN/Random-Forest decision models for irrigation & water treatment
B1: Emissions, Global Warming, and (Agro)forestry <i>Soil ⇌ Atmosphere (GHG fluxes); Soil ⇌ Vegetation/ Biodiversity (agroforestry interactions)</i>	*Carbon sequestration & N ₂ O reduction (Regulating) *Micro-climate & biodiversity habitat via agroforestry soils (Supporting)	SDG 2; SDG 6; SDG 12; SDG 13; SDG 15	Life Cycle Inventory (carbon accounting); Forest Management; Meta-analysis; Trade-off analysis; Environmental economic analysis
B2: Life Cycle Assessment and Carbon Footprint <i>Soil ⇌ Atmosphere (carbon cycling); Soil ⇌ Water (non-point pollution)</i>	*Climate regulation through quantified emission reductions & soil-carbon strategies (Regulating)	SDG 12; SDG 13; SDG 15	Best-Management-Practice (BMP) frameworks; LCA with Monte-Carlo uncertainty; Decision-Support Systems; Cost-Benefit Analysis; Water-/Carbon-Footprint tools
C1: Environmental Monitoring and Land Use Management <i>Soil ⇌ Water (run-</i>	*Erosion/sediment control & watershed run-off buffering (Regulating) *Water-flow	SDG 6; SDG 11; SDG	GIS & remote-sensing Decision-Support Systems; Scenario/factor/regression

Table 3 (continued)

Thematic Cluster (Interdependent Natural Capitals)	Linked Ecosystem Services	SDGs	BMA (Interdisciplinary) Concepts, Methods, Tools & Approaches
<i>off, watershed); Soil ⇌ Biodiversity/Vegetation; Soil ⇌ Atmosphere (dust/GHG)</i>	regulation in catchments (Regulating) *Habitat provision & long-term soil formation (Supporting)	13; SDG 15	analysis; SWAT watershed modelling
C2: Waste Management and Resource Recovery <i>Soil ⇌ Waste/Organic-matter flows; Soil ⇌ Water (leachate control); Soil ⇌ Atmosphere (GHG from waste)</i>	*Organic fertiliser & energy generation from waste (compost, biogas, biochar) (Provisioning) *Pollution and GHG reduction through sustainable waste handling (Regulating) *Soil-fertility improvement via recycled nutrients (Supporting)	SDG 2; SDG 3; SDG 6; SDG 11; SDG 12; SDG 13	Life-Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA); Environmental & Health Risk Assessment; Multivariate/Principal-Component analytics for decision support
C3: Mining Operations and Ecosystem Health <i>Soil ⇌ Mineral extraction residues; Soil ⇌ Water (leachate, wetlands); Soil ⇌ Biodiversity (post-mining restoration)</i>	*Leachate purification in constructed wetlands (Regulating) *Erosion control on spoil heaps (Regulating) *Habitat/soil restoration on reclaimed land (Supporting)	SDG 6; SDG 8; SDG 9; SDG 12; SDG 13; SDG 15	Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA); Resilience/sustainability management protocols
C4: Ecological Economics <i>Soil ⇌ Water; Soil ⇌ Biodiversity; Soil ⇌ Atmosphere (through sustainable production and circular-economy loops)</i>	*Sustainable biomass/food production in agro-ecology & urban agriculture (Provisioning) *Emission reduction & resource-efficiency gains (circular economy) (Regulating) *Maintenance of multifunctional ecosystem capacity (Supporting) *Cultural & economic valuation of soil services (Cultural)	SDG 2; SDG 9; SDG 11; SDG 12; SDG 13; SDG 15	Risk-management frameworks; Productivity; Consumer behaviour; Economic evaluation; Policy-analysis tools
D1: Innovative Agricultural Techniques and Use Efficiency <i>Soil ⇌ Water (irrigation, drainage)</i>	*Higher crop water productivity & yields (Provisioning) *Water conservation/quality protection (reduced runoff, leaching) (Regulating) *Enhanced nutrient-use efficiency & cycling (Supporting)	SDG 2; SDG 6; SDG 12	LCA for irrigation options; Economic-benefit & water-footprint evaluation; Strategic modelling/uncertainty analysis; Variability; Forecasting; Cleaner Production; Strategy; Entrepreneurship
D2: Sustainable Agriculture and Food Security <i>Soil ⇌ Water; Soil ⇌ Biodiversity; Soil ⇌ Atmosphere</i>	*Food supply & security through resilient cropping (Provisioning) *Climate-resilient farming & nutrient	SDG 1; SDG 2; SDG 12; SDG	AHP/TOPSIS multi-criteria decision methods; GIS-based planning; Circular-economy and eco-efficiency metrics;

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

Thematic Cluster (Interdependent Natural Capitals)	Linked Ecosystem Services	SDGs	BMA (Interdisciplinary) Concepts, Methods, Tools & Approaches
(climate-adaptive farming)	recycling (Regulating) *Long-term soil-health and biodiversity support (Supporting)	13; SDG 15	Willingness to Pay; Innovation; Supply Chain Management; Blockchain traceability tools
D3: Soil Health, Agricultural Productivity, and Profitability Soil \rightleftharpoons Biodiversity; Soil \rightleftharpoons Atmosphere (soil-carbon, GHG)	*Greater crop yield & quality (Provisioning) *Soil-fertility restoration & SOC storage (Supporting) *Carbon sequestration/pollution reduction co-benefits (Regulating)	SDG 2; SDG 8; SDG 12; SDG 13; SDG 15	Emergy analysis; Adoption & extension frameworks; Profit-soil KPI dashboards; Productivity; Structural-Equation Modelling (SEM)
D4: Data Mining and Technology in Agriculture Soil \rightleftharpoons Water (smart irrigation); Soil \rightleftharpoons Atmosphere (emission optimization)	*Productivity gains via precise input management (Provisioning) *Reduced fertiliser/pesticide losses & emissions (Regulating) *Real-time soil-crop intelligence for decision-making (Supporting/Cultural)	SDG 2; SDG 9; SDG 12; SDG 13; SDG 15	IoT-enabled monitoring; Machine-learning decision support; Big-data analytics for farm management; Fuzzy Logic; Genetic Algorithm; Neural Networks; Deep Learning; Prediction; Decision Making
D5: Nanotechnology in Sustainable Agriculture Soil \rightleftharpoons Water (nano-irrigation, contaminant control); Soil \rightleftharpoons Nutrient/mineral cycles	*Higher nutrient-use efficiency & yields (nano-fertilisers) (Provisioning) *Lower non-point pollution and runoff (Regulating) *Enhanced microbial diversity/nutrient cycling in soils (Supporting)	SDG 2; SDG 6; SDG 9; SDG 12; SDG 13; SDG 15	Competitiveness; Efficiency; Environmental performance

Petzold, 2020). Soil provides both private and public benefits such as farmer income and ecosystem services; however, distinguishing between the two can be challenging. Certain management practices can enhance soil quality, benefiting both private and public purposes, while others may prioritize one purpose at the expense of others (Turpin et al., 2017). In safeguarding environmental and human well-being while advancing sustainable land management practices, it becomes important to improve ecosystem services including food provision, biomass production, water purification and treatment, air quality regulation, climate regulation, erosion control, waste treatment, pest and disease management, and nutrient cycling (Adhikari and Hartemink, 2016). By recognizing the pivotal role of soil functions in supporting essential ecosystem services, researchers can contribute to the development of holistic approaches that address both short-term agricultural needs and long-term sustainability goals (Pereira et al., 2018). This systemic perspective ensures the resilience of soil ecosystems and promotes the broader sustainability agenda, fostering a balance between environmental stewardship and socio-economic progress.

From a policy and development lens, SDGs such as Zero Hunger (SDG 2), Clean Water and Sanitation (SDG 6), Responsible Consumption and Production (SDG 12), Climate Action (SDG 13), and Life on Land (SDG15) are repeatedly invoked across clusters, signaling their centrality in soil-related sustainability debates. These connections affirm

the foundational role of soil in enabling multiple development pathways and support growing calls for its formal integration into environmental and economic accounting systems.

Moreover, by integrating soil health and ecosystem service considerations into broader sustainability frameworks, including the UN's SDGs, research attempts can better inform policy-making processes and foster synergies between SHMPs and global sustainability initiatives. As also recommended by Adhikari and Hartemink (2016), future research in soil and ecosystem services should prioritize the enhancement of soil health while aligning with the SDGs set forth by the UN. This entails comprehensively examining the organization of actors and actions related to soil health and its ecosystem services.

At the same time, the review reveals critical BMA gaps. While numerous technical and operational tools are employed, from LCA and AHP to Decision Support Systems (DSS) and data-driven technologies, higher-order managerial and organizational approaches are still underrepresented (Ingram et al., 2022). Concepts such as sustainable or circular business models, strategic stakeholder engagement, and systemic planning are infrequently addressed. In particular, two identified themes (i.e., clusters A1 and A3) do not explicitly engage with managerial tools, suggesting missed opportunities for integration. Even where BMA tools are present, they often serve a diagnostic or evaluative function rather than informing broader strategic or governance frameworks (see Table 3).

Further, the findings imply the necessity of investigating broader socio-economic aspects (Keesstra et al., 2018). Integrating social, environmental, and economic dimensions is key to advancing sustainable soil management practices (Martinho, 2019). While environmental sustainability has often been the primary focus of the literature, attention to the social dimension, particularly connecting people with soils, is essential. With 95 % of our food coming from soils, raising awareness and addressing the social aspect of soil health is paramount (Montanarella and Panagos, 2021). Social disconnection from soil has increased due to urbanization trends and shifts away from agricultural livelihoods. Considering this disconnect, innovative ways need to be found to reconnect citizens with soils, such as highlighting how healthy soils are connected to healthy food (Montanarella and Panagos, 2021). The rise in organic farming and consumption indicates a growing interest in sustainable food production systems among citizens, presenting opportunities to raise awareness about the need for sustainable soil management (Montanarella and Panagos, 2021). Incorporating sustainable business models and environmental-economic accounting standards can further enhance this awareness and drive positive change (Comte et al., 2022; Ingram et al., 2022; Keesstra et al., 2018). Taking a holistic system-based approach to soil management that addresses the needs of people and the planet can be facilitated by emphasizing the interconnectedness of social, environmental, and economic factors (Keesstra et al., 2018).

Overall, the findings suggest that soil is not merely an environmental variable but a strategic lever for sustainability. However, the soil research often lacks the managerial, organizational, and institutional perspectives necessary to drive transformative change. Table 3, by consolidating these insights, offers a comprehensive synthesis of how soil connects across ecological, developmental, and managerial dimensions, highlighting both synergies and gaps that warrant further scholarly and practical attention.

4.3. Knowledge gaps and directions for future research and practice

A core aim of this review was to evaluate how well soil research has integrated BMA concepts, methods, and frameworks. The analysis of clusters and their mapping to ecosystem services, SDGs, and BMA tools (summarized in our final synthesis table) reveals a mix of encouraging strengths and significant gaps. On the strengths side, the literature demonstrates solid utilization of various management and decision-support tools in soil studies. We see frequent use of LCA to account for soil

impacts in product supply chains and farming systems, indicating that soil considerations are being folded into broader environmental management and accounting practices (Lemming et al., 2010; Notarnicola et al., 2017). Likewise, operations research and decision analysis techniques, notably AHP and other MCDA methods, have been successfully applied to soil management and land use problems, from prioritizing conservation practices to designing sustainable agriculture interventions (Gebre et al., 2021). The prevalence of these tools suggests that researchers are actively bringing quantitative BMA methodologies into the soil context, enabling more objective and structured decision-making.

4.3.1. Business-strategy lens

Our review uncovered several areas where BMA integration remains weak or absent. Chief among these is the scarcity of higher-level business model and strategic management frameworks in the soil literature. While operational tools are present, very few studies have applied concepts like business model innovation, stakeholder management, or organizational change to questions of soil sustainability. For instance, virtually no cluster in our analysis dealt with how farmers and firms (e.g., agri-businesses) might redesign their business models to account for soil stewardship or how soil considerations inform long-term business strategy (França et al., 2017; Hansson et al., 2023; Keith et al., 2016). This lack is striking, given that soils are fundamental to industries like agriculture, food, forestry, and even climate mitigation markets. The absence of explicit strategy-oriented research implies that soil remains largely a technical or compliance issue in the literature, rather than a source of competitive advantage or strategic risk/opportunity (França et al., 2017; Hansson et al., 2023).

Additionally, there is a critical research gap regarding corporate engagement with soil in value chains. We found that the current literature does not deeply explore how businesses manage soil resources or ecosystem services within their supply chains and operations, nor how soil degradation or improvements translate into business risks and opportunities. Surveys have shown that many businesses do not yet recognize their dependence on soil ecosystem services (Mikhailova et al., 2020). The scant attention to topics like supply chain standards for soil health, corporate investment in regenerative soil practices, or soil-related corporate social responsibility indicates a silo between soil science and business strategy.

Another gap is the limited use of organizational and policy frameworks that could connect micro-level soil practices to macro-level governance. Despite the global emphasis on sustainable development, we see few studies linking soil initiatives to instruments such as sustainability standards, incentive structures, or private-public partnerships. Recently, there is a nascent movement in policy and industry circles to develop business models for soil health (e.g., the EU's mission to ensure 75 % of soils are healthy by 2030), which encourages innovative business approaches to soil stewardship (Lal et al., 2021). Early ideas include using tools like the Triple-Layered Business Model Canvas to design soil-friendly enterprise models (Alerasoul et al., 2024; Wood et al., 2024), but such ideas have yet to penetrate the academic literature in a meaningful way.

To address these gaps, we recommend operationalizing an integrative/balanced sustainable business model (SBM) as a configuration that jointly optimizes (i) long-term soil health, (ii) firm profitability and risk, and (iii) social legitimacy and knowledge continuity—aligned with the linkages summarized in Table 3. In practice, practitioners should map this onto a lean SBM canvas: Value proposition (resilient yields and verified soil-health outcomes); Key activities (low-disturbance soil structuring, precision in-soil water management, in-situ amendments, soil-safe machinery, data-guided decisions, and Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification [MRV]); Partners (farmer cooperatives, OEMs/service providers, water and waste actors, certification bodies); Revenues/Costs (target yield-risk reduction, input savings, and price premiums/compliance-cost avoidance against capex/opex for equipment, MRV,

and training); and KPIs (soil infiltration, soil organic matter/SOC, water-use efficiency, fuel use and machinery passes, yield stability, profitability/risk, and ecosystem-service indicators). Framed as above, soil stewardship can be treated as a strategic capability rather than a compliance add-on (Alerasoul et al., 2024; Wood et al., 2024).

4.3.2. The need for interdisciplinary research

Despite the growing recognition of soil's vital role in sustainability, truly interdisciplinary integration between natural sciences and business disciplines remains limited. The current literature often reflects one-way borrowing of concepts rather than the co-development of integrated frameworks. For example, environmental research may mention "economic incentives," or business studies may reference "ecosystem services" to contextualize environmental issues, yet few studies succeed in fusing these perspectives into shared theoretical models (Reinecke et al., 2024). This review reveals a critical need for deeper collaboration between soil scientists and management scholars, through hybrid analytical approaches, co-authored studies, and sector-spanning case research. Siloed thinking remains pervasive, especially between natural and social sciences, and continues to inhibit the holistic understanding required to address soil degradation and sustainability challenges.

Conceptually, scholars should work toward frameworks that integrate ecological and management theories. For example, SBM approach, resource-based, or dynamic capabilities perspectives could be expanded to recognize soil ecosystems as critical sources of value and constraint (Hart and Dowell, 2011; Hansson et al., 2023; Keith et al., 2016; Whiteman et al., 2013). Similarly, adopting sustainability-oriented concepts such as planetary boundaries or ecosystem thresholds can enrich corporate performance models. These efforts require methodological innovation, combining qualitative inquiry (e.g. case studies of agribusiness adaptation) with systems modeling to account for the multi-scalar dynamics of soil–economy interactions (D'Amato et al., 2024; Hansson et al., 2023).

4.3.3. Toward integrated, systems-thinking approaches

A systems thinking mindset offers a promising corrective. Rather than viewing soil in isolation, researchers and decision-makers must treat it as part of a complex adaptive system involving climate, water, biodiversity, and human well-being (Amundson et al., 2015; Dominati et al., 2014). Our findings suggest that sustainable soil management requires coordinated, multi-sector action. Encouragingly, some studies exemplify this integrative shift. For instance, Hou et al. (2020) describe "social learning" networks that empower farmers as change agents, supported by scientists and policymakers. These collaborative arrangements show how blending technical expertise with practical and institutional knowledge can accelerate the co-creation of innovative soil management practices (Alerasoul et al., 2024; Wood et al., 2024).

To achieve a systemic approach, collaboration among disciplines and stakeholders is recommended to address changes in farming practices, given the interconnectivity between soil health and agricultural operations (Martinho, 2019). Fragmented knowledge infrastructure among disciplines, and limited collaboration among stakeholders hinder progress towards ambitious soil strategy objectives, emphasizing the need for holistic approaches aligned with policy goals (Bouma et al., 2022; Inam et al., 2015; Thorsøe et al., 2023). This entails bridging the gap between research and policy implementation, fostering collaborations between soil and social scientists, businesses, and policymakers, and engaging public awareness about soil-related challenges (Evans et al., 2022).

The prevailing agricultural efficiency paradigm recognized in the literature often views soil health solely as a means to address environmental degradation and enhance agricultural economic viability. However, this perspective oversimplifies the value of soil health, neglecting its broader societal and intrinsic worth as articulated in farmers' narratives regarding their motivations and incentives (Friedrichsen et al., 2025). To advance soil health research, there is a need to shift away from this narrow focus on instrumental values and embrace a more holistic

approach that acknowledges the relational values embedded within soil health (Friedrichsen et al., 2025). This entails broadening the scope of soil health outcomes to encompass solutions addressing the multifaceted social impacts of agriculture and ecosystem services on human well-being (Normyle et al., 2023; Sandifer et al., 2015). To achieve this paradigm shift, scholars need to recognize farmers and indigenous stewards as knowledge creators and transmitters in agricultural science (Ingram, 2008). By integrating diverse intrinsic motivations and relational values associated with soil health, future research can better illuminate pathways to foster human well-being within agricultural systems (Friedrichsen et al., 2025; Normyle et al., 2023; Restall and Conrad, 2015).

Firms in agriculture, food systems, mining, and land development should embed soil sustainability into their strategies. This includes setting soil health goals, aligning land-use targets with global environmental frameworks, and adopting natural capital accounting to measure and disclose soil-related impacts (Guerry et al., 2015). Governments, in turn, must strengthen regulatory and incentive-based frameworks for soil conservation (Koch et al., 2013). This could involve payments for ecosystem services, subsidies for regenerative practices, and reforms aligning private incentives with public soil stewardship goals. Education and capacity-building, training managers, farmers, and professionals in systems thinking and soil governance, are also essential to translate awareness into practice and ensure the long-term sustainability of soils (Lal et al., 2021).

4.3.4. Innovation and technological levers

The findings also hold significant implications for technology and innovation management, particularly in advancing sustainable agriculture initiatives and achieving the SDGs through digital transformation. Policymakers and governments are urged to prioritize the promotion and implementation of digital and AI-based technologies in soil health practices and agri-food supply chains to improve crop yields, reduce carbon footprints, and enhance input efficiencies. Initiatives may include incentives and subsidized loans to encourage farmers' adoption of advanced machinery and green technologies, thereby fostering more sustainable agriculture and food systems (Abbate et al., 2023). Moreover, sustainable business models in the agri-food sector must undergo a cultural shift towards community-focused and open-minded innovation, with government support playing a pivotal role in enabling this transition (Abbate et al., 2023). Integrating digital technologies into soil and agriculture practices offers great potential to address environmental challenges, increase food production, and contribute meaningfully to global efforts to alleviate hunger and combat climate change.

In parallel with these digital transformations, attention must also be given to mitigating environmental pollutants, such as toxic gases, suspended particles, heavy metals, and organic substances, which threaten human health by permeating food chains and accumulating in biota (Ibrahim et al., 2016). To address these challenges, the development, management, and institutional support of efficient monitoring and remediation technologies are critical. Among emerging solutions, nanotechnology stands out for its ability to manipulate materials at the nanoscale, enabling novel properties and applications. With broad utility across sectors like food, energy, and pollution treatment, nanotechnology offers transformative potential for enhancing conventional remediation methods and informing related policies, thereby advancing environmental sustainability efforts (Ibrahim et al., 2016).

Nature-based solutions for soils can be framed as non-imitative, process-aligned technologies that reinforce soil structure, water regulation, nutrient cycling, and contaminant immobilization while remaining economically viable. Within this portfolio, several approaches have been reported, including (i) subsurface soil structuring and aggregation with low disturbance; (ii) precision in-soil water management; and (iii) in-situ incorporation of structuring or nutrient amendments and safe by-products. These approaches are often complemented by soil-safe machinery, decision support systems, and MRV

frameworks that make soil outcomes credible for both policy and business models. As one example within this broader portfolio, the Biogeosystem Technique (BGT) bundles (a) intra-soil milling for artificial aggregation in the illuvial horizon, (b) sequential discrete in-soil watering, and (c) in-situ milling with applied structuring inputs. Reported effects include aggregation gains, water savings, heavy-metal passivation, and yield improvements under specific conditions (Okolelova et al., 2022; Kalinitchenko et al., 2024, 2025). We include BGT as one option alongside other soil-health-oriented approaches, noting context dependence and the need for comparative evaluations with standardized MRV.

4.4. Limitations

Upon reflection on the methodology employed and the insights garnered it is imperative to acknowledge both the advantages and limitations inherent in bibliometric analysis. While our approach effectively delineated various intellectual streams within the literature, it is essential to recognize that bibliometric analysis, particularly co-word analysis, may fall short in providing a nuanced interpretation of content due to its technical nature (Donthu et al., 2021). However, by complementing this analysis with a review of influential papers through a hybrid approach, we mitigated this limitation to some extent, enhancing our understanding of prevailing topics and their temporal evolution.

Furthermore, it is pertinent to acknowledge the limitations associated with the Scopus indexer, particularly concerning the all-keyword approach, which operates based on predefined criteria. This inherent subjectivity may introduce biases and overlook certain nuances present in the literature. Besides, Scopus assigns subject classifications to journals based on the All Science Journal Classification (ASJC) method, placing them into subject categories and subcategories (Kim and Jeong, 2023). However, due to the complexities involved in journal classification and the evolving nature of scholarly communication, discrepancies or biases in subject assignments can occur, leading to potential limitations in database searches and analyses. Additionally, as with any systematic literature study, factors such as the coverage of the database and the application of inclusion/exclusion criteria necessitate careful subjective considerations (Alerasoul et al., 2022a).

5. Conclusion

This interdisciplinary review highlights that the interface between soil science and business management is increasingly pivotal for both ecosystem services and sustainable development. Through co-word analysis of the literature, we identified two main research domains bridging these fields. The first centers on Soil Health, Environmental, and Technical Management, encompassing studies on sustainable soil use, pollution remediation, and agricultural best practices that underscore the multifunctional value of soil health. The second domain revolves around Circular Economy, Ecosystem Services, and Sustainable Development, reflecting scholarship that situates soil as natural capital within broader systems of resource cycling and ecosystem service provision.

Together, these domains affirm that soil science is no longer a siloed ecological concern; it is increasingly recognized as a foundation for sustainability transitions (interrelated with water, atmosphere, and biodiversity) and SDGs (Dominati et al., 2014; Lal et al., 2021). Soils are increasingly recognized as a natural capital asset providing essential ecosystem services that support human well-being and the global sustainability agenda (Robinson et al., 2017). Recent assessments show that soils have a positive influence on every SDG, either directly (e.g. food security, climate action) or indirectly by supporting Nature's Contributions to People (Smith et al., 2021). However, this positive contribution cannot be taken for granted. Poorly managed or degraded soils can just as easily undermine ecosystem services and hinder progress on

multiple SDGs (Smith et al., 2021). In essence, maintaining soil integrity is not just an ecological imperative but a managerial and societal priority, one that influences supply chains, commodity markets, and the stability of the biosphere that businesses and communities depend on (Guerry et al., 2015; McBratney et al., 2014). By mapping this terrain, our study demonstrates how soil science knowledge is becoming ever more relevant to socio-economic interests and sustainability objectives.

We provided an integrative overview of how soil research intersects with business and management imperatives, and it charts a strategic research frontier for scholars and practitioners alike. We have shown that applying systems thinking to soil, recognizing it as natural capital that underpins ecosystem services and economic activities, is both necessary and increasingly acknowledged in the literature (Dominati et al., 2014). At the same time, we have highlighted the need to move beyond technical analyses toward interdisciplinary frameworks that bridge soil science with management strategy and public policy (Han et al., 2020). Soil, as a priceless natural asset, must be managed not only with scientific expertise but also with strategic foresight and cross-sector collaboration (Baveye et al., 2016).

Our findings reinforce that soil is a cornerstone of sustainability as natural capital, and they call for concerted interdisciplinary efforts to ensure that the management and policy domains fully embrace soil stewardship (Dominati et al., 2014; Han et al., 2020; Keith et al., 2016). Such efforts will not only bridge the current divide between soil science and BMA but also help embed soil's health and productivity at the heart of sustainable development strategies, a fitting response to the grand challenges of our time. This review, therefore, serves as a roadmap highlighting where we stand and where we must go: toward a future where soil's vital services are valued in our economic systems, guided by systems-thinking frameworks that connect natural and business worlds, and driven by an appreciation that caring for soil is integral to caring for our collective future (D'Amato et al., 2024).

Appendix

Appendix. Clusters identified through the Authors-Keyword analysis (analyzed via VOSViewer v.1.6.20 for the sample N = 6,910, f (frequency) > 5 → 636 keywords).

Cluster	Keywords
A1	bearing capacity, biocementation, biodegradable, biodegradation, biosolids, black cotton soil, bricks, California bearing ratio, carbonation, case study, CBR, cement, characterization, clay, compaction, compressive strength, concrete, consolidation, construction, construction materials and methods, cost, covid-19, degradation, durability, embankment, environmental protection, environmental remediation, erosion control, excavation, expansive soil, expansive soils, FEM, field test, finite-element method, fly ash, geosynthetics, geotechnical properties, geotextile, green infrastructure, landfill, landfill mining, landslide, lime, liquefaction, mechanical properties, microstructure, mining, moisture, content, numerical simulation, permeability, physical properties, plasticity index, polymer, reclamation, recycling, red mud, rehabilitation, reinforced soil, reinforcement, resilient modulus, retaining wall, sand, seepage, SEM, settlement, sewage sludge, shear strength, slope stability, soil burial, soil compaction, soil improvement, soil reinforcement, soil stabilization, soil-structure interaction, stabilization, strength, subgrade, tailings, triaxial test, unconfined compressive strength, unsaturated soil, waste management, waste recycling, water absorption, water content
A2	bioaccumulation, bioavailability, biofuel, Brazil, cadmium, compost, contaminated soils, crop rotation, economic benefit, electrical conductivity, environmental impact assessment, environmental risk, ethanol, fertility, fruit quality, greenhouse gases, health risk assessment, humic acid, hydrochar, hydrothermal carbonization, immobilization, laterite, lead, life cycle analysis, municipal solid waste, Nigeria, nutrient, nutrients, organic carbon, peat, ph, phytoextraction, phytoremediation, porosity, potassium, rare earth elements, Romania, soil conditioner, soil pollution, soil quality, soil remediation, solid waste, topsoil, wheat
A3	anionic surfactants, artificial soil, biopolymers, carbon black, clothes, contamination, cotton fabrics, detergency, detergents, energy, enzymes, eutrophication, foam washing, kinetics, laundering, oily soil, palmitic acid, particle, particles, protease, protein, removal, scanning electron microscope, soil, soil amendment, soil deposition, soil removal, soil washing, soils, sorption, substrate, surfactant, surfactants, washing, zeolite
A4	accumulation, acid mine drainage, adsorption, arsenic, artificial neural networks, bauxite residue, cellulose, embodied energy, global warming potential, groundwater, heavy metal, heavy metal contamination, hydraulic conductivity, irrigation, leaching, mechanical property, mechanism, random forest, revegetation, salinization, technical efficiency, technology adoption, transport, water retention, water scarcity, water treatment
B1	agroforestry, bacteria, biodiesel, carbon, carbon sequestration, China, denitrification, density, diversity, economic analysis, ecosystem services, evaporation, evapotranspiration, forest management, foundation, fungi, global warming, grazing, greenhouse, greenhouse gas emission, heavy metal pollution, intercropping, invest model, Iran, life cycle inventory, meta-analysis, methane, microbial community, microorganism, model, N2O emission, nitrate, nitrogen, nitrogen removal, nitrous oxide, numerical modeling, organic fertilizer, pile foundation, plant, precipitation, rhizosphere, soil temperature, soybean, trade-offs, vegetation, water consumption, wetlands
B2	best management practices, carbon footprint, climate change, composite, conservation, cost-benefit analysis, decision support systems, developing countries, fertilizer, LCA, life cycle assessment, livestock, mitigation, Monte Carlo simulation, natural resource management, nonpoint source pollution, organic food, paddy fields, phosphorus, reliability, renewable energy, sensitivity analysis, soil carbon sequestration, substance flow analysis, sustainability assessment, swat model, uncertainty analysis, water footprint, watershed management
C1	air pollution, Anthropocene, biomass, carbon neutrality, carbon storage, change detection, climate change, mitigation, correlation, cropland, decision support system, deforestation, economic development, ecosystem service, ecosystems, environmental health, environmental impacts, environmental management, environmental monitoring, environmental pollution, erosion, Ethiopia, factor analysis, geographic information system (GIS), GHG emissions, GIS, greenhouse gas, hydrology, infiltration,

(continued on next page)

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alireza Alerasoul: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Shayegheh Ashourizadeh:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Valentina Cristiana Materia:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During manuscript preparation, the authors used AI-assisted tools (e.g., OpenAI models) to improve readability and language. The authors reviewed and edited all content and take full responsibility for the integrity and accuracy of the manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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(continued)

Cluster	Keywords
	Israel, land cover, land cover change, land use, land use change, Landsat, landscape, microplastics, modelling, natural resources, palm oil, peatland, pesticides, poverty, public health, regression analysis, remote sensing, restoration, runoff, RUSLE, scenario analysis, sediment, sediment yield, sludge, soil and water conservation, soil conservation, soil degradation, soil erosion, soil loss, soil organic carbon, spatial analysis, surface runoff, sustainable land management, SWAT, Tanzania, urbanization, watershed
C2	activated carbon, anaerobic digestion, antibiotic resistance genes, biochar, bioeconomy, bioenergy, biogas, chromium, composting, design, digestate, dust, ecological risk, environmental impact, fertilization, food waste, gasification, geopolymer, GHG emission, health risk, heavy metals, life cycle impact assessment, manure, metals, migration, mining waste, multivariate analysis, organic waste, organic wastes, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, principal component analysis, pyrolysis, recycle, remediation, reuse, risk assessment, sequential extraction, source apportionment, spatial distribution, speciation, vermicomposting, waste, water
C3	bottom ash, construction and demolition waste, copper, environmental sustainability, impact assessment, India, nickel, resilience, soil protection, sustainable management, wastewater, zinc
C4	abiotic stress, adaptation, agricultural production, agroecology, arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, Australia, biocontrol, biocontrol agent, bioremediation, construction equipment, construction management, consumer behaviour, contaminated soil, costs, ecology, ecosystem, emissions, environmental justice, environmental policy, environmental safety, equity, evaluation, externalities, health, industrial waste, intensification, legumes, optimization, pgpr, phosphate solubilization, phosphogypsum, plant growth, plant growth promotion, productivity, risk, risk management, safety, sustainable development, sustainable production, urban agriculture, Vietnam, vulnerability
D1	ammonia volatilization, Ansys, artificial neural network, biodegradability, cleaner production, crop yield, cropping systems, drainage, economic benefits, engineering education, entrepreneurship, finite element method, food, forecasting, geotechnical engineering, grain yield, ground improvement, Jordan, life cycle assessment (LCA), life cycle assessment, modelling, nitrate leaching, nitrogen use efficiency, nutrient cycling, simulation, soil structure interaction, strategy, tensile strength, tillage, tomato, transportation, ultimate bearing capacity, uncertainty, variability, water productivity, water quality, water use efficiency
D2	Africa, AHP, analytic hierarchy process, bioethanol, blockchain, circular economy, climate change adaptation, decision-making, drought, eco-efficiency, Energy, environment, farmers, food security, geographic information system, innovation, land-use change, management, multi-criteria analysis, nutrition, organic agriculture, Pakistan, plastic waste, road construction, salinity, sugarcane, supply chain, sustainability, sustainable agriculture, technology, Thailand, TOPSIS, tourism, toxicity, vertical farming, willingness to pay
D3	adoption, agricultural productivity, Bangladesh, biodiversity, biofertilizer, biofuels, biomass production, climate, coal mining, conservation agriculture, conservation tillage, conventional tillage, cotton, crop production, cropping system, cultivation, driving factors, Energy analysis, enzymatic activity, food safety, geographically weighted regression, green revolution, greenhouse gas emissions, growth, land reclamation, liquid fertilizer, maize, microalgae, mulberry, mulching, nutrient recovery, organic, organic matter, pollution, profitability, quality, rice, soil analysis, soil carbon, soil carbon storage, soil contamination, soil fertility, soil health, soil organic matter, soil ph, soil properties, soil salinity, soil texture, spatial variability, structural equation modeling, subsurface drainage, sustainable intensification, sustainable remediation, vegetables, vermicompost, wastewater treatment, winter wheat, yield
D4	agriculture, aquaponics, Arduino, artificial intelligence, automation, big data, biorefinery, classification, cloud, clustering, crop, crops, data mining, decision making, deep learning, drip irrigation, energy efficiency, farming, fertilizers, fuzzy logic, genetic algorithm, GSM, humidity, humidity sensor, hydroponics, image processing, internet of things, internet of things (IoT), IoT, machine learning, medicinal plants, mobile application, monitoring, NDVI, neural network, neural networks, pest control, precision agriculture, prediction, rainfall, raspberry pi, sensors, slope, smart agriculture, smart farming, smart irrigation, soil moisture, soil moisture sensor, solar energy, SVM, temperature, temperature sensor, water management, wireless sensor network, WSN
D5	building materials, community, competitiveness, efficiency, environmental performance, forestry, land degradation, microbial diversity, nano fertilizers, nanomaterials, nanoparticles, nano pesticides, nanosensors, nanotechnology, nutrient use efficiency, organic farming, phytotoxicity, rural development, stabilized soil, sustainable, sustainable construction

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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